

D.4.3: First period dissemination report and second period dissemination plan

Author:

Kate Fernie, MDR

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Partner in charge of the deliverable: **PIN**

Editor for PIN: **Kate Fernie**

Quality review: **Holly Wright, UoY ADS**

Contributing partners: **All partners**

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Document History

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on dissemination activity in ARIADNE during months 1 to 18, referenced against the initial dissemination plan (D4.2), and an update of the project dissemination plan for period two, months 18 to 36.

The mission of the ARIADNE is to bring together and integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new technologies as an integral part of archaeological research methodology.

The initial dissemination plan (D4.2) set out a strategy during period one to raise awareness about the ARIADNE project and the research infrastructure amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organizations
- Research institutions represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties including deans, directors etc.
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines and the wider scientific community
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission
- Media and the public at large

These aims continue in period two.

The objectives of the initial dissemination plan were to:

- Define the stakeholder community, identify its interests and the main channels for communication and networking activities
- Build and extend the contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts
- Inform the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media
- Provide an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, a brochure and other materials for use by the partners
- Present the project at relevant national and international events

Section 2 of this report describes dissemination activity during months 1-18 (including how stakeholders have been involved in the project), the dissemination materials produced, dissemination of news and information, activity on the social networks and the project website, events, publications and activities around transnational access and training. Monitoring of the objectives and success indicators set in the initial dissemination plan, show that targets were met and in most cases exceeded. The involvement of end users in workshops, summer schools and in completing the user needs survey has been particularly positive.

Section 3 of this report provides an update to the project dissemination plan for period two, this update takes into account the results of activities during period one. During period two the objectives of the dissemination strategy will be to:

- Build the Stakeholder **contact database** and **following** on social media;

- Develop appropriate **materials** targeted to specific audiences;
- Coordinate partner activities to maximize **impact**;
- Provide qualitative and quantitative **indicators**.

The dissemination plan describes a range of activities to support these objectives.

The project dissemination plan is a live document and it will be updated again at month 36 to inform dissemination planning for the period ahead.

2 Dissemination activity during the first period

This section of the report provides a review of dissemination activity during months 1-18 against the initial dissemination plan (D4.2).

2.1 Stakeholders

The initial dissemination plan (D4.2, pages 9-11) defined the following groups amongst the ARIADNE stakeholder community:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research, or management responsibilities relating to project activities
- Research institutions active in the field as represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties such as deans, directors etc.
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission
- Media and the public at large

During the first period, ARIADNE set out to raise awareness of the project amongst each of these groups.

As part of the Community Building activities of WP2, SRFG carried out a survey of user needs. The survey was advertised widely through international mailing lists and other channels to **research institutions**, and resulted in 700 **researchers** and **repository managers** completing an online survey and giving their feedback to the project.

Special Interest Groups have been established by WP2 for project partners and external experts with an interest in:

- 3D and Visualisation
- Archaeological Research Practices and Methods
- Remote Sensing and Spatial Data
- Scientific Data
- Excavation and Monument Data
- Grey Literature
- Metadata and Semantics
- Linked Data

These groups have met, in person and virtually, and have begun to survey the state-of-the-art in their field and have provided input for the ARIADNE user needs survey, exchanged information, identified issues and planned future activities. A section of the ARIADNE project website has been set up to hold information about the Special Interest Groups: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Community/Special-Interest-Groups>.

During 2014 ARIADNE launched Trans National Access to online services offered by three partners:

- Archaeology Data Service: ArchSearch
- AIAC (the International Association for Classical Archaeology): FASTI Online
- Deutsches Archäologisches Institut: ARACHNE and ZENON

Two TNA training workshops have been organized by ARIADNE partners for researchers and students to provide an introduction to these online services; the workshops were held at EAA 2013 and CAA2014. Notably, FASTI Online was recognized by the Archaeological Institute of America, receiving an award for “outstanding work in digital archaeology” in January 2014; the presentation of the award provided an opportunity for AIAC to speak about both FASTI Online and ARIADNE to the members of the Institute.

Physical access to ARIADNE TNA services was launched in summer 2014 with 3 inaugural summer schools on 3D Documentation, the CIDOC-CRM and design of Archaeological Datasets taking place. The call for access was advertised internationally to researchers and advanced-level students via mailing lists. A training workshop was organized by ARIADNE at EVA London 2014 to promote physical access by researchers to TNA services.

There have been a large number of presentations by partners at conferences, in seminars and in project meetings. A workshop at CHNT 2013 to introduce ARIADNE and its services to participants.

ARIADNE has also been actively engaging with **international networks** and research **infrastructures**. The project launch included presentations from the DCH-RP (Digital Cultural Heritage Roadmap for Preservation), DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure) and CENDARI (Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure) alongside presentations from the board of the European Association of Archaeologists and about the wider context for the ARIADNE. Since that time ARIADNE has exchanged cooperation agreements with:

- CENIEH, Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, Spain
- CNRS-FRANTIQ, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
- IAI-UJA, Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Arqueología Ibérica. Universidad de Jaén, Spain
- IAPH, Archaeological Institute of the Andalusian Heritage, Spain
- MCH- Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo, Norway

and is in the process of discussing cooperation agreements with:

- DGPC- Direção-Geral do Património Cultural, Portugal
- Aarhus University, Denmark

ARIADNE has also exchanged Memorandum's of Understanding with:

- EAGLE project
- DCH-RP

And has established associations with two international organisations:

- FAIMS (Federated Archaeological Information Management Systems) funded by the Australian National eResearch Collaboration Tools and Resources program.
- Digital Antiquity and tDAR (the Digital Archaeological Record) which is a non-profit organization based at Arizona State University in the US.

2.2 Resources amongst the consortium and externally

The ARIADNE consortium consists of partners in 16 countries including Sweden, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria. During the first period, the partners have been very active in disseminating news about the project. Activities included:

- Creating links to the ARIADNE website from the partners' own site (all partners)
- Giving presentations at national and international events (see below for details)
- Organising ARIADNE workshops at international conferences (see below for details)
- Distributing ARIADNE dissemination materials
- Distributing notices about ARIADNE activities to mailing lists
- Writing articles about ARIADNE activities for in-house newsletters
- Contributing articles to the ARIADNE newsletter
- Disseminating news and information about ARIADNE via the social networks
- Participating in meetings organized by research infrastructures, projects and international initiatives and giving presentations about ARIADNE and/or distributing materials

2.3 Information and news

The project has disseminated information and news about the project's activities and related areas via the project website, a project newsletter, social media channels and (to a more limited extent) to the press.

A dedicated section of the project website has been established for news:

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website's news section. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Services', 'Community', 'Events', 'Resources', and 'News'. Below the navigation bar, the page title is 'ARIADNE' with a logo. The main content area is titled 'News' and contains three news items:

- Call for papers** (22 Jul 14): The call for papers for VAST2014 is open until 10th August. VAST this year will address the theme of Virtual Research Environments, i.e. "innovative, web-based, community-oriented, comprehensive, flexible, and secure working environments conceived to serve the needs of modern science" in the domains of humanities, cultural heritage and archaeology.
- 2D/3D Documentation for Archaeology Summer School** (11 Jul 14): From June 23rd to 27th, 2014, CNR-ISTI hosted in Pisa the Summer School on "2D/3D Documentation for Archaeology" as part of the ARIADNE Transnational Access (TNA) activities.
- Stakeholder Survey Results Published** (1 Jul 14): Earlier this year, ARIADNE carried out an extensive survey to identify the Network's user requirements for kind of e-infrastructures, tools and services to be provided. This consisted of two online questionnaires, one targeted at archaeological researchers and directors of research institutions, and the second targeted the managers or directors of data repositories. 692 researchers and 52 repository managers completed the questionnaires.

On the right side, there is a sidebar with a list of project activities and partners, including 'Flights into the Past', 'SENESCHAL Project', 'ARIADNE Funds Training for DAI Archaeologist', 'Structural Analysis Training Courses', 'Linked Open Data', 'ArcheoLandscapes welcomes ARIADNE as associated partner', 'Newsletters', 'DARIAH welcomes ARIADNE', 'ARIADNE at the AIAC Congress in Merida', 'From Preserving Data to Preserving Research', 'TPDL CIDOC CRM Workshop', and 'ACM JOCCH call'. At the bottom right, there are social media sharing icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter.

This section is used to publish short news articles and announcements (such as calls for papers and participation in events): <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News>. In addition, news posted on the project's Twitter account is published on the home page of the project's website.

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE project website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for About, Services, Community, Events, Resources, and News. Below this, there are three main content columns. The first column, titled 'About Ariadne', features a 'Read More' button and a paragraph of text describing the project's goal to integrate archaeological research data. The second column, 'Latest News', has a 'See All' button and lists three news items with their dates: 'Call for papers' (Jul 22 2014), '2D/3D Documentation for Archaeology Summer School' (Jul 11 2014), and 'Stakeholder Survey Results Published' (Jul 1 2014). The third column, 'Tweets', includes a 'Follow' button and displays three tweets from the @Ariadne_Network account, mentioning NKOS workshops and registration details.

2.3.1 Project newsletter

Three issues of the project newsletter have been produced during the first 18 months of the project:

- July 2013
- February 2014
- July 2014

Each issue of the newsletter has highlighted activities by ARIADNE, partner activities and related projects such as DARIAH, SENESCHAL and the ARCHES project.

The newsletter is distributed directly to 150 stakeholders who have registered to be on our mailing list, and indirectly via notices to mailing lists and on Twitter.

The newsletters are available from the project website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/Newsletters>.

2.3.2 Social networks

2.3.2.1 Twitter

@Ariadne_Network was established on Twitter in April 2013. By 31st July 2014 there were:

- 208 followers
- @Ariadne_Network is following 103 Twitter users
- @Ariadne_Network had made 320 tweets since the start of the project

Sixty of ARIADNE's tweets have been retweeted. (Source Retweet.co.uk).

The top 10 retweets show there was a high level of interest in the Stakeholder Survey and training opportunities.

Rank	Subject matter	No. of retweets	Date
1	Stakeholder Survey launch	15	21 Nov 2013
2	Archaeological summer school deadline extension to 31/5/14	12	8 April 2014
3	Archaeological summer school deadline extension 16/6/14	10	19 May 2104
4	Applications open for summer schools	9	27 Feb 2014
5	Last call for registration for archaeological datasets summer school	7	11 June 2014
6	Online Resources workshop at CAA	6	9 April 2014
7	12 fellowships in textual scholarship...	6	14 Dec 2013
8	ARIADNE summer school applications open	6	14 Feb 2014
9	Fasti Online nomination for award	6	30 Oct 2013
10	Two PhD studentships	5	30 May 2014

The graph (from <http://www.twitonomy.com/>) for the date range 18 April 2013 to 06 Aug 2014) reveals that the project is mentioned by other users on a fairly steady basis. The peak in mentions in early September 2013 coincided with the ARIADNE Workshops at the EAA annual conference.

ARIADNE's following on Twitter has built up over the first eighteen months of the project. @ARIADNE_Network has gradually established itself as a source of useful information for archaeologists and in the process gathered followers who are retweeting ARIADNE news.

The Twitter accounts for ADS (Update and Chatter) and DARIAH mention the ARIADNE Network frequently, and many of the partners promote the project through their own organisational and personal accounts.

The potential of social media to reach large numbers of users is illustrated by the dissemination of the Stakeholder Survey. The survey was disseminated through the ARIADNE website, LinkedIn Group and feed, as well as through discussion forums and e-mail lists. ARIADNE partners promoted the survey through their own channels with many posting notices on their Facebook pages, Twitter accounts and other social media (see below for details). For example, an article was published on Culturaltalia and added to the RSS Feed. This was then promoted on Culturaltalia Social network channels:

- Tweeted to 1450 followers.
- Posted on Facebook to 9,842 fans
- Posted on Linked-in group with 2693 members
- Posted on Google+ to 240 followers
- Emailed to our 2,000 registered users

The impact of Twitter on the User Needs Survey was particularly noticeable as it was retweeted by many different archaeology-related feeds during the first few days, reaching over 10,000 users. This led to around 1,200 people clicking on the questionnaire link and almost 700 completed returns.

The potential reach of @ARIADNE_Network on Twitter (i.e. the network of tweeters and their followers) is nearly 150,000 Twitter users.

		tweets	following	followers	listed	
	@Ariadne_Network Ariadne_Network	320	103	208	11	17 mentions
	@ADS_Update ADS	780	243	2,687	131	16 mentions
	@Julian62523002 Julian D Richards	588	137	1,021	54	15 mentions
	@ADS_Chatter ADS Chatter	1,057	135	391	20	13 mentions
	@DARIAHeu DARIAH-EU	868	48	1,018	56	11 mentions
	@DigCurationUnit DigitalCurationUnit	1,360	446	320	22	6 mentions
	@MappaProject Mappa Project	1,365	277	695	35	4 mentions
	@jessogden Jessica Ogden	1,941	570	1,146	82	3 mentions
	@archaeologyuk Archaeology for All	1,211	863	8,769	237	3 mentions
	@verdewek César González-Pérez	5,712	128	160	10	2 mentions

Source: Twitonomy.com

2.1 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn Group has been set up for the ARIADNE Network and currently has 27 members. The group has been relatively inactive so far, however it has potential to become more used for discussions by the ARIADNE Special Interest Groups.

Number of members: 27

Number of discussions: 16

2.2 Slideshare

A Slideshare account has been set up for ARIADNE however by 31st July only one presentation, the Introduction to the ARIADNE Network by Franco Niccolucci had been uploaded to Slideshare to date.

Number of views 2077

Number of downloads 4

2.3 YouTube

A presentation of the project ARIADNE - Conference 'kick-off' in Rome - February 7, 2013 was made available on YouTube on 6th March 2013 and has had 34 views.

URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9x1-4Ddux8E>.

The image shows a screenshot of a YouTube video player. At the top left is the YouTube logo with 'GB' and a search bar. The video frame shows two people at a conference table with a blue screen in the background. Overlaid text reads 'Progetto Ariadne - kick-off 7 febbraio 2013'. The video progress bar shows 0:03 / 4:47. Below the video, the title is 'Presentazione del progetto Ariadne - Conferenza 'kick-off' a Roma - 7 febbraio 2013'. The channel name is 'PIN - Polo Universitario Città di Prato' with a 'Subscribe' button showing 28 subscribers. The view count is '35 views'.

2.4 Dissemination materials

An initial set of dissemination materials was produced in the first months of the project including the project logo:

The materials also included a template for PowerPoint presentations, a presentation giving an introduction to the project, and a large poster was produced by the Discovery Programme for partners to take to CAA 2013, which took place in early April.

Holly Wright (Archaeology Data Service, UK)
hollyw@archaeologydataservice.ac.uk

Anthony Corne (The Discovery Programme, Ireland)
acorne@discoveryprogramme.ie

Julian Richards (Archaeology Data Service, UK)
julian.richards@archaeologydataservice.ac.uk

Franco Nicolucci (INdA, Italy)
nicolucci@inda.it

ARIADNE

www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

ARIADNE (Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe) brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology. There is now a large availability of archaeological digital datasets that all together span different eras, domains and regions; more are continuously created as a result of the increasing use of IT. They are the accumulated outcome of the research of individuals, teams and institutions, but form a vast and fragmented corpus and their potential has been constrained by difficult access and non-homogeneous perspectives.

ARIADNE will enable trans-national access of researchers to data centres, tools and guidance, and the creation of new Web-based services based on common interfaces to data repositories, availability of reference datasets and usage of innovative technologies. It will stimulate new research avenues in the field of archaeology, relying on the consortium, re-use and integration into current research of the outcomes of past and on-going field and laboratory activities. Such data are scattered amongst diverse collections, datasets, unpublished fieldwork records (grey literature), and in publications. The latter still being the main source of knowledge sharing. ARIADNE will contribute to the creation of a new community of researchers ready to exploit the contribution of Information Technology and to incorporate it in the body of established archaeological research methodology.

To achieve this result the project will use a number of integrating technologies that build on common features of the currently available datasets, and on integrating actions that will build a vibrant community of use.

Why ARIADNE?

Need of Integration
- Go beyond scientific or administrative borders
- Integrate datasets oversteering in scope
- Access unpublished information

Data Deluge
- Growth in archaeological projects
- Growth in size of project datasets

Willingness to share, store and re-use
- 450,000 downloads from ADS grey literature repository over 6 years

Joint Research Activities - Developing Advanced Integrated Services

Innovative Tools & Services	Linked Data	Addressing Complexity
<p>The existence of the integrated infrastructure will stimulate the creation of new datasets and services, based on the semantic tools, services and methodologies. The integration of existing datasets, the creation of new ones and the production of synthetic ones will improve a continuous and structured stream of data for archaeological research.</p>	<p>Develop and provide research tools for connecting, linking and browsing datasets across ARIADNE</p> <p>Develop semantic services enabling the creation of all-age according to individual research needs</p> <p>Adopt and export ARIADNE data providers to the creation and publishing of Linked Data of their datasets</p>	<p>Develop extensions to CDROM/CDRW for specific archaeological applications, allowing for variations of their characteristics</p> <p>Develop digital maps, tables and interactive documents of complex datasets and metadata resulting on archaeological datasets</p>
Interoperability	Data Mining	Natural Language Processing
<p>Adapt and integrate existing infrastructure into ARIADNE</p> <p>Build a range of solutions to enable interoperability in languages, protocols, mappings, APIs and internal dataset structures</p> <p>Adopt, select, design and deploy services within the integrated infrastructure to enable the provision of online services to researchers</p>	<p>Develop systems of relevance and enabling tools to mine related archaeological data and beyond</p> <p>Custom tooling based upon usage patterns and needs</p> <p>Retain and link research resources with dynamically retrieved ARIADNE datasets (OpenAPI)</p>	<p>Build the effectiveness of natural language processing-based services and tools for archaeological applications</p> <p>Develop automated procedures for linking and adding semantic descriptions to large numbers of existing grey literature</p> <p>Design and implement communication services, providing natural language descriptive research from aggregation of linked data</p>

Transnational Access

Availability, Usable, Useful

Designed expert facilities within the project consortium will enable the integration of researchers from the skills to and expertise within research by use of archaeological data collection, management and integration

Build user-oriented with respect to critical phases of their research

Offer effective use of the research infrastructure

Support knowledge integration

Legacy Data & Dataset Design

Scientific Datasets

3D Documentation

Online Access

Community Building

Involve, Stimulate, Collaboration

Research resources in a substantial component of Research Infrastructures. ARIADNE will create a community of use involving the creation, sharing and reuse of digital data.

Take into account the needs and interests of all stakeholders

Adopt a user-centred and user-orientable approach to infrastructure creation

Share resources of the

Forming good practices in data sharing

Sharing to discover new and existing of IT availability

Reduce the costs of community and collaboration

Developing eArchaeology

Innovate, Explore, Experiment

ARIADNE will enable archaeological and related research communities to be at the forefront of data driven research, making use of research services that could not be addressed before, allowing researchers to discover new data and to explore new methods and allowing for collaborative, bottom-up research. Addressing current Europe and beyond. In particular, a new generation of researchers will be trained that are ready to exploit to the best use the digital datasets and services for IT-enabled archaeological research (archaeology) made available by ARIADNE

Develop innovative European archaeological datasets and knowledge applications to advance the research process

Copy out pilot eArchaeology applications within the ARIADNE

Project Partners

Archaeology Data Service (UK), Discovery Programme (Ireland), INdA (Italy), etc.

MiBACT-ICCU coordinated the preparation of a first version of a project leaflet presenting the project and its main activities in summer 2013.

The leaflet was made available for printing, and has been distributed by partners at a series of events.

2.4.1 Project website

The ARIADNE website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) was launched in month one of the project. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and related projects. The public part of the website now includes:

- About – the project, consortium and activities
- Services – Trans National Access, Online Services, Training opportunities
- Community – joining the network, special interest groups, associated projects
- Events calendar
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- News – news stories, bulletins and newsletter
- Contacts

During the reporting period, new sections have been created on the website and new content has been added, as materials have been produced and the project's activities have advanced.

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for About, Services, Community, Events, Resources, and News. The 'Resources' section is active, displaying a list of links and reports. The page includes a search bar, a language selector (English), and a social media sharing widget. The main content area lists several reports and publications, including 'ARIADNE FP7 factsheet', 'Presentation - "The ARIADNE Project"', 'First ARIADNE report on users' needs - summary of the main findings', 'ARIADNE, 2014, D2.1 First report on users' needs', 'ARIADNE, 2013, D3.1 Initial report on standards and on the project registry', 'ARIADNE, 2013, D3.2 Report on project standards', and 'ARIADNE, 2014, D3.3 report on data sharing policies'.

Project resources are published on the ARIADNE website in a dedicated section:
<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

Web statistics

Google Analytics was set up to record visits to the ARIADNE website as soon as the site was launched.

Between 1st February 2013 and 31st July 2014, there were 15,066 sessions by 9,346 visitors. Visitor numbers increased substantially from October 2013, peaking in January 2014 and then falling to a rate of just under 800 per month.

English is the first language for 42% of ARIADNE website visitors, 13% German and 14% Italian, 5% French, 3% Greek and 2% each for Dutch, Spanish and Russian.

Europe is the main location of ARIADNE website users at 84% with a further 6% from North America.

Please note: While there are systems in place to prevent visits from site administrators being registered in the statistics (by IP and by website account), these systems are not 100% reliable and may result in inflated visit counts from the UK. It is also worth noting that Google Analytics does not record visits from users with JavaScript disabled. There are no accurate figures for the percentage of users with JavaScript disabled, but it is generally considered to be somewhere between 2% to 3%.

Percentage of visits to the ARIADNE website by country:

Top 10 referrers

ARIADNE referrals are dominated by Social Media – Facebook, Twitter and Linked account for 25%. The project’s online Stakeholder Survey was responsible for another 7% (SurveyGismo). Fasti Online, the Archaeology Data Service, DAI and ISTI CNR also appears in the top 10 referrers and together referred almost 20% of visits to the ARIADNE website (see figure below).

Referrals to the website lead to a total of 5245 user sessions.

Referral Source	Sessions	% Total
facebook.com	736	14.03%
t.co	375	7.15%
surveygizmo.com	350	6.67%
archaeologydataservice.ac.uk	277	5.28%
vcg.isti.cnr.it	245	4.67%
fastionline.org	192	3.66%
york.ac.uk	186	3.55%
dainst.org	171	3.26%
m.facebook.com	138	2.63%
linkedin.com	134	2.55%
Other	2441	46.54%
Total	5245	100.00%

The most frequently viewed pages on the ARIADNE site during period one were the Home page, the About page, the Call for Participation in TNA access for 2014, and Resources and Services.

In total 49,667 page views were recorded during period one.

Page	Pageviews	% Total
Home	9621	19.37%
About	3522	7.09%
Services2014-TNA-call	3169	6.38%
Resources	2760	5.56%
Services	2422	4.88%
Events	2233	4.50%
News	1835	3.69%
Partners	1528	3.08%
Community	1363	2.74%
userlogin	567	1.14%
Other	20647	41.57%
Total	49667	100.00%

2.5 Dissemination activities

2.5.1 Events

Partners have reported participation in over 90 conferences and events during the first 18 months of the project. These activities include the organisation of one-day workshops, conference sessions, the presentation of individual papers and posters, invited talks and key-note speeches, distribution of project literature, and face-to-face meetings with representatives of networks, projects and organisations to discuss collaboration agreements. The full list of activities is presented below (see Annex 2), a few highlights are:

ARIADNE workshop at EAA Pilsen

- The first ARIADNE online TNA workshop was organized by ADS and formed a pre-conference workshop at EAA Pilsen, 4 September 2013
- A session on New Digital Developments in Heritage Management and Research was organized by PIN and ADS as part of EAA Pilsen, 5 September 2013
- An ARIADNE workshop at CHNT 2013, Vienna, 11-13 November 2013 was organized by SRFG with OEAW.
- The second ARIADNE online TNA workshop was organized by ADS at CAA 2014 on 22 April 2014
- PIN organised the first ARIADNE physical TNA workshop at EVA London 2014 on 10 July 2014
- In addition to these ARIADNE training workshops, partners have participated in training workshops organized by others:
 - PIN presented the project at the Heritage School on Digital Cultural Heritage, which was organized by CYI-STARC in Nicosia, 27-30 May 2013
 - TPDL workshop: Practical Experiences with CIDOC CRM and its Extensions (CRMEX) – three ARIADNE papers accepted. Valetta, Malta – 26 September 2013

PIN has had regular meetings with research infrastructures, projects and research institutions to discuss opportunities for collaboration. Athena-RC has presented ARIADNE at various meetings of

the COSCH network (COST Action TD 1201, www.cosch.info).

Partners have begun planning for dissemination activity in the next period, which includes submitting proposals for workshops and sessions to international conference committees for consideration.

MiBACT-ICCU, with support from PIN, is organizing an ARIADNE international one-day conference on research infrastructures in November 2014, as an official event under the Italian presidency of the EU.

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Viale Castro Pretorio 105, Conference Hall
Simultaneous translation Italian-English

ICCU
ARIADNE

2.5.2 National events

There have been a series of events organized at a national level (see the list of dissemination activities in Annex 2). Some highlights include:

- Il SITAR nella Rete della Ricerca Italiana Verso la conoscenza archeologica condivisa- Terzo Convegno, 23-24 May, 2013. Presentation of ARIADNE by PIN.
- LII National Archaeological Conference, Bulgaria, May 28-31, 2013. Presentation of ARIADNE by NIAM.
- Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past, UK, 6th July 2013. Poster by UoY-ADS and Discovery.
- CAA Konferensen, CAA-Sweden, 2-4 December 2013. Presentation by CNR.
- CAA-Germany annual meeting, 14-15 February 2014. Presentation by DAI.
- Launch of DARIAH-GR, 7 April 2014. Presentation by PIN.

In addition to events, there have been face-to-face meetings taking place at national level. For example, DISCOVERY has been having regular meetings with heritage stakeholders in Ireland who can potentially offer data to ARIDANE including the National Museum of Ireland, The Heritage

Council, the National Monument Survey of Ireland, National Roads authority (NRA), Dublin City Council (DCC) and the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI). PIN attended a meeting with the Danish Humanities Research Infrastructures in Aarhus in May 2014.

2.5.3 Publications

2014

Gonzalez-Perez, C. and P. Martín-Rodilla (2014) “Integration of Archaeological Datasets through the Gradual Refinement of Models”, at the 42nd Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) (Paris, France, 22-25 April 2014). (forthcoming)

Martín-Rodilla, P. and C. Gonzalez-Perez (2014) “An ISO/IEC 24744-Derived Modelling Language for Discourse Analysis”, at the 8th IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS) (Marrakech, Morocco, 28-30 May 2014). (forthcoming)

2013

Amico, N., P. Ronzino, A. Felicetti, F. Niccolucci (2013) Quality management of 3D cultural heritage replicas with CIDOC-CRM, Vladimir Alexiev, Vladimir Ivanov, Maurice Grinberg (eds.): Practical Experiences with CIDOC CRM and its Extensions (CRMEX 2013) Workshop, 17th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2013), Valetta, Malta, September 26, 2013, CEUR-WS.org/Vol-1117, pp 61-69, urn:nbn:de:0074-1117-1.

Felicetti, A., Tiziana Scarselli, M.L Mancinelli, F. Niccolucci (2013) Mapping ICCD Archaeological Data to CIDOC-CRM: the RA Schema, Vladimir Alexiev, Vladimir Ivanov, Maurice Grinberg (eds.): Practical Experiences with CIDOC CRM and its Extensions (CRMEX 2013) Workshop, 17th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2013), Valetta, Malta, September 26, 2013, CEUR-WS.org/Vol-1117, pp 11-22, urn:nbn:de:0074-1117-1.

Gilissen V. (2013) Past the Opening: building towards the present, on-going dissemination of Dutch archaeological data as part of the DANS archive. In: Conference proceedings Opening the Past 2013: Archaeology of the Future. <http://depot.knaw.nl/14882/>

Gonzalez-Perez, C. and P. Martín-Rodilla (2013) “A First Attempt at Describing, Reusing and Disseminating Archaeological Methodological Knowledge”, at the 19th European Association of Archaeologists Annual Meeting (EAA) (Pilsen, Czech Republic, 4-8 September 2013).

Gonzalez-Perez, C (2013) “Modelling Temporality and Subjectivity in ConML”, at the 7th IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS) (Paris, France, 29-31 May 2013).

Gonzalez-Perez, C., P. Martín-Rodilla and R. Blanco-Rotea (2013) “Expressing Temporal and Subjective Information about Archaeological Entities”, at the 41st Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) (Perth, Australia, 25-28 March 2013).

Niccolucci, F. and J. D. Richards (2013) ARIADNE: Advanced Research Infrastructures for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe. A new project to foster and support archaeological data sharing. In: The European Archaeologist, Issue No. 39, Summer 2013. http://e-a-a.org/tea/rep1_39.pdf

Niccolucci, F. and J.D. Richards (2013) *ARIADNE: Advanced Research Infrastructure For Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe*, International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing 7.1-2, pp 70–88, Edinburgh University Press, DOI: 10.3366/ijhac.2013.0082.

Niccolucci, F. (2013) Un'infrastruttura di ricerca per l'archeologia: il progetto ARIADNE, Digitalia 2(2013), 154-161.

Palmas, G., N. Pietroni, P. Cignoni and R. Scopigno (2013) A computer-assisted constraint-based system for assembling fragmented objects, Digital Heritage 2013, forthcoming proceedings, [pre-print pdf](#).

Ronzino, P., N. Amico, A. Felicetti and F. Niccolucci (2013) European standards for the documentation of historic buildings and their relationship with CIDOC CRM, Vladimir Alexiev, Vladimir Ivanov, Maurice Grinberg (eds.): Practical Experiences with CIDOC CRM and its Extensions (CRMEX 2013) Workshop, 17th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2013), Valetta, Malta, September 26, 2013, CEUR-WS.org/Vol-1117, pp 70-79, urn:nbn:de:0074-1117-1.

Vlachidis, A and D. Tudhope (2013) The Semantics of Negation Detection in Archaeological Grey Literature. Metadata and Semantics Research (eds E. Garoufallou, J. Greenberg) . Communications in Computer and Information Science Volume 390, 2013, pp 188-200 (M7).

Vlachidis, A and D. Tudhope (2013) The Semantics of Negation Detection in Archaeological Grey Literature. Metadata and Semantics Research (eds E. Garoufallou, J. Greenberg) . Communications in Computer and Information Science Volume 390, 2013, pp 188-200.
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2012

Richards, J.D. (2012) Digital Infrastructures for Archaeological Research: A European Perspective, published in the CSA Newsletter XXV (2), September 2012.
<http://csanet.org/newsletter/fall12/nlf1202.html>

Geser, G. and F. Niccolucci (2012) Virtual museums, digital reference collections and e-science environments. In: Uncommon Culture, Vol. 3, no. 5/6, 12-37
<http://uncommonculture.org/ojs/index.php/UC/article/view/4714/3677>

Technical reports and specifications

Gonzalez-Perez, C. and C. Hug (2014) "ConML Technical Specification" version 1.4.3 (30 April 2014), available from http://www.conml.org/Resources_TechSpec.aspx.

Gonzalez-Perez, C (2013) "CHARM White Paper" version 1.0.3 (22 November 2013), available from <http://www.charminfo.org/Resources/Technical.aspx>.

Gonzalez-Perez, C (2013) "CHARM Extension Guidelines" version 1.0.1 (22 November 2013), available from <http://www.charminfo.org/Resources/Technical.aspx>.

2.5.4 Guides to Good Practice and Case studies

The first ARIADNE case study was published during 2013:

Schäfer, Felix F., Deutsches Archäologisches Institut, "Selection and Retention of Files in Big Data Collections: The Example of the Pergamon Excavation of the DAI Istanbul", available from: http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/CS_ARIADNE-DAI-Schafer.

News about the case study was reported on the ARIADNE website and via Twitter.

The ARIADNE news article was linked to a post by Felix Schäfer on the ADS blog and was also reported by ADS on their Facebook site and Twitter accounts.

Since the case study was published on 1st August 2013 to 31st July 2014, the web statistics show that it received 120 unique page views from 114 unique visitors, with a total of 148 page views and visitors spending on average 54 seconds per visit.

Unique page views graph:

The website statistics show that visitors came to the Case Study from existing ADS Guides to Good Practice, search engines, external websites and by typing the URL directly into a web-browser.

2.6 Transnational Access and training

During the first project period there has been dissemination activity to support the promotion of the transnational access (TNA) and training being offered by ARIADNE. These activities have included disseminating calls for participation in training events, calls for participation in TNA summer schools, notices about the launch of online services, news items via the project newsletter, twitter and other social media, and creating content in the Services section of the project website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Services>.

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Services', 'Community', 'Events', 'Resources', and 'News'. Below this, the 'Services' section is highlighted. The main content area contains the following text:

Services

ARIADNE provides services for archaeologists to enable trans-national access to the research infrastructure. These services include online databases and training resources, training workshops and placements in participating research organisations to enable researchers to gain pan-European experience.

Online Services

Ariadne includes leading portals which provide integrated access to archaeological datasets.

Transnational Access

Ariadne will advertise calls for researchers to apply for physical access to leading research laboratories that focus on:

- Dataset design and implementation
- Integration and interoperability of datasets
- Multimedia management in archaeological datasets
- Metadata mapping and interoperability
- Design of scientific datasets
- 3D documentation of fieldwork and artefacts.

Training

Training will be offered to researchers in the use of the research infrastructure and specific technologies. All training opportunities will be listed in the right hand side column.

The right-hand sidebar contains a list of recent events: 'TNA Workshop EVA 2014', 'Online Services', 'Transnational Access', '2014 TNA call', and 'ARIADNE Workshop @ EAA 2013'. At the bottom of the sidebar, there are social media sharing icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, Google+, and Twitter.

2.6.1 Physical access

As part of its Transnational Access (TNA) activities, the ARIADNE project advertised a call for researchers to apply to participate in three summer schools to carry forward their own research:

- Mapping existing datasets to the CIDOC CRM; 26-30 May 2014
- 2D/3D documentation for archaeology, 23-7 June, 2014
- Design of archaeological datasets, 14-18 July, 2014

The call for applications was advertised widely in Europe and internationally and closed on 13th March 2014. The call for applications for the Design of archaeological datasets was later extended to 16th June 2014.

35 researchers submitted applications to participate in the three summer schools; applications were reviewed by an international selection panel:

- Peter Biehl, SUNY Buffalo, and European Association of Archaeologists
- Gary Lock, University of Oxford and President, Computer Applications in Archaeology
- Laurent Romary, INRIA & HUB-IDSL and DARIAH
- Franco Niccolucci, PIN, Project Coordinator
- Julian Richards, ADS, Deputy Project Coordinator
- Achille Felicetti, PIN
- Carlo Meghini, CNR
- Roberto Scopigno, CNR

20 researchers were selected by the panel and were offered ARIADNE fellowships, 2 researchers were unable to accept as other commitments meant they could not participate in the summer schools. The 18 fellows who participated in 2014 were:

Name	Institution	Country	School
Patrick Marko	University of Graz	Austria	CRM
Roberta Ferrito	University of Reading	Great Britain	CRM
Emmanuelle Morlock	CNRS HiSoMa Laboratory, Lyons	France	CRM
Mercedes Morita	Centro de Investigaciones Opticas and Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Argentina	3D
Andres Uueni	State conservation centre, Kanut	Estonia	3D
Laura Stelson	University of Bonn	Germany	3D
Erika Cappelletto	Heidelberg University	Germany	3D
Georgios Ionnakis	Democritus University of Thrace	Greece	3D
Tom Trienen	Groningen Archaeological Institute	Netherlands	3D
Yuan Yuan	Göteborg University	Sweden	3D
Freya Horsfield	University of Birmingham	Great Britain	3D
Dries Nollet	Visual Dimension bvba	Belgium	3D
Carlotta Capurro	Visual Dimension bvba	Belgium	Data
Darío Peña Pascual	Universidade Santiago de Compostela	Spain	Data
Michelle Pfeiffer	University of Heidelberg	Germany	Data

In addition, places at the summer schools were offered to three young researchers from Italian institutions who were not eligible to receive TNA bursaries (as the access was provided in Italy).

2.6.2 Online access

During 2014 ARIADNE launched Trans National Access to online services offered by three partners:

- Archaeology Data Service: ARCHSEARCH
- AIAC (the International Association for Classical Archaeology): FASTI Online
- Deutsches Archäologisches Institut: ARACHNE and ZENON

The launch of these services was promoted via news on the project website and via social networks. The training workshops (see 2.6.3 below) also helped promote the services to researchers and students.

The **ADS web service** was launched in 1996 and has seen a gradual increase in users year on year. The ADS uses Piwik Web Analytics to collate and study their website metrics. During the 17 month period from 1st February 2013 to 31st July 2014, ADS had 393,964 unique visitors who carried out a total of 3,306,823 actions, including 234,607 downloads and 3,030,646 page views.

During this period ADS modified the website's direct access filter to take account of users finding PDFs and images directly via Google. This resulted in a dramatic difference between the average monthly users (14,000) in the first half of the period (February – 14th September 2013) and the average monthly users (35,000) for second half (15th September 2013 – 31st July 2014) as can be seen in the figure below.

Detailed analysis of the ADS web statistics revealed the impact of the ARIADNE training workshops. CAA 2014 (22nd – 25th April) increased traffic to the website by over 25%. Similar increases were noted in relation to CHNT 2013 and the ARIADNE workshop held prior to EAA 2013. There was a very significant spike in views of the ADS research pages following the ARIADNE workshop before EAA 2013 (the green box in the figure below shows the peak in view of ADS's main research page).

FASTI Online was launched in early 2009. The user rates have been fairly static with the average number of users last year being 1,343 per month. However, there has been an increase in activity

since the start of this year when the average rose to over 1,500 users per month. There have been some significant usage peaks, the first being during the week of the 10th – 16th November, the same week as the CHNT 2013. There are several more peaks on a monthly basis from January to April 2014 with a high of 974 users for the first week in June.

The **ARACHNE Online** service was first available from late December 2007. The following graphic of users shows the steady increase in the numbers of users. By 2014, the average number of users per month is just under 12,000. For the 18 month period one Feb 2013 – 31 July 2014, the visitor rate to the ARACHNE website has been fairly stable. Repeat visitors and new visitors are around 50% each. During this period, there were 387,390 sessions by 198,876 users, who generated 2,966,813 page views.

2.6.3 Training

Training workshops on Data Management planning and use of Online Resources for Archaeology were organized by UoY-ADS and delivered with the support of SRFG, SND, DANS, DAI and AIAC at:

- EAA Pilsen 2013 (4-8 September 2014): SRFG, SND, DANS, DAI, AIAC and ADS
- CAA Paris 2014 (April 2014): DAI, AIAC and ADS (and tDAR from the US)

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[Ariadne](#) > [News](#) > [Ariadne's first training workshop](#)

Ariadne's first training workshop

By [Kate Fernie](#) Tue 10 Sep 2013

Participants at the Ariadne training workshop held in Pilsen

The **ARIADNE** project organised a workshop on **Data Management Planning and Online Resources for Archaeology** which was held just prior to the start of the [European Association of Archaeologists \(EAA\) annual conference](#) in Pilsen, Czech Republic on Wednesday 4 September.

This workshop was attended by around 25 participants and project partners. Its main aim was to introduce strategies for effective data management and planning, and to present some of the online data resources available to researchers through ARIADNE.

The workshop began with a welcome from Julian Richards of the Archaeology Data Service who also gave a brief introduction to the

ARIADNE project.

Guntam Geser of [SFRG](#) then gave a presentation on "**Open Data Publication**" talking about the drivers, criteria, behaviours and benefits to researchers of publishing their data online in a way which is accessible (not necessarily without registration), reusable (in open formats) and openly licenced. Guntram spoke about open data publication as a progression from self-archiving linked to an open access journal publication and the impact of data intensive research. High level policy drivers are also important:

Flights into the Past

SENESCHAL Project

ARIADNE Funds Training for DAI Archaeologist

Structural Analysis Training Courses

Linked Open Data

ArcheoLandscapes welcomes ARIADNE as associated partner

Newsletters

DARIAH welcomes ARIADNE

ARIADNE at the AIAC Congress in Merida

From Preserving Data to Preserving Research

TPDL CIDOC CRM Workshop

ACM JOCCH call

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2.7 Monitoring indicators for period one

Success indicators

Description		Month 18 target	Month 18 actual
Stakeholder involvement	No of institutions	50	<p>9 institutions have (or are in the process) of exchanging cooperation agreements with ARIADNE.</p> <p>2 associations established with international organisations.</p> <p>2 collaborations with external projects on good practice guidance.</p> <p>11 other collaborations with organisations or professional associations.</p> <p>26 senior researchers and data managers were interviewed for user-needs survey reflecting on the needs of their institutions.</p> <p>23 organisations are partners in ARIADNE.</p> <p>50 organisations, not including ARIADNE partners, were involved during the period.</p>
User involvement	No of participants	75	<p>60 workshop participants</p> <p>20 TNA summer school participants</p> <p>692 researchers and data managers completed user-needs survey.</p> <p>772 users have participated in ARIADNE activities.</p>
Project website	Visitors	6000	Between 1 st February 2013 and 31 st July 2014, there were 15,066 sessions by 9,346 visitors
Research infrastructure online services	Anonymous users		No targets were set for period one as the integrated portal is due to come online in period two. Online access to three existing external services was launched during the period.
Research	Registered		No activity to report in this period; the

infrastructure online services	users		ARIADNE integrated portal will come online during period two.
Social networks	No of members	500	208 Followers on Twitter 27 members on LinkedIn
Presentations at international events	No. of presentations*	1000	ARIADNE has been presented by partners at over 90 events during period one. The number of participants has been recorded for 24 events; 1810 users participated in c 30% of all events.
Good practice guides accessed	No. unique visitors	100	The first ARIADNE case study was viewed by 114 unique visitors during the period.
Newsletters	Readers	100	150 subscribers who receive the newsletter directly.

* This appears to be a mistake in the initial dissemination plan, as 1000 presentations over an 18 month period seems far higher than could realistically be expected in this kind of project. It seems likely that the intention was to set a target for participants.

Achievement of period one objectives:

Objective	Description & planned activity	2013-14 activity
Objective 1	Establishing the project website: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Designing and building the project website and social media accounts to welcome and inform end users and stakeholders about the research infrastructure. 	The website was established in the first month of the project and has been developed and improved throughout.
Objective 2	Building and extending the stakeholder database: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing the contact database. Cooperating with existing communities such as EAA (European Association of Archaeologists) and CAA (Computer Applications in Archaeology) and others to develop the contact database. Maximising contacts through 	<p>Registrations on the project website have been linked to a database for distributing news to stakeholders, and in addition a Twitter account has been established and a following is being built up to build up additional contacts.</p> <p>The project has been cooperating with EAA, CAA and others to disseminate news about the project's activities.</p> <p>Partners have been active in sharing</p>

	the partners' networks to disseminate news and build the database.	news about the project and its activities via their websites, newsletters, and social media account.
Objective 3	<p>Informing the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities and transnational access to the infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing the project presence in the social networks. • Designing the Project Newsletter and producing three issues per annum. • Use of Mailing lists and Social Networks to disseminate news and drive traffic to the project website. • Press Notices – project launch 	<p>Accounts have been set up for the project on Twitter and LinkedIn, with some media also being uploaded to SlideShare, YouTube and Flickr.</p> <p>The project newsletter has been designed, but only two issues have been produced per annum.</p> <p>Twitter is being used regularly to disseminate project news, calls and other information. The impact of retweeting of ARIADNE news by partners and other followers dramatically extends the reach of the stakeholder database to around 150,000. Social media is driving traffic to specific pages on the website, for example the 2014 call for TNA access.</p> <p>Press notices were prepared to announce the launch of the project, and translated by partners into several languages.</p>
Objective 4	<p>Informing the research community about transnational access and training opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing the transnational access selection panel. • Preparing the first call to researchers to put forward proposals for access. • Use of dissemination channels to advertise training opportunities to researchers. 	<p>External experts were invited to participate in the TNA user selection panel.</p> <p>The 2014 call for TNA access was prepared and disseminated to researchers. Three TNA summer schools were organized and evaluated as being successful by the participating researchers.</p> <p>Three TNA training workshops took place and, along with other workshops and the TNA access, calls for participation were disseminated widely to researchers via social media.</p>
Objective 5	<p>Providing an initial set of dissemination materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project brochure • Introductory PowerPoint 	The initial set of project dissemination materials was provided as planned.

	<p>presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project poster 	
Objective 6	<p>Presenting the project at relevant international and national events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project presentations at international events • ARIADNE Workshops 	<p>The project has been presented at more than 90 international and national events.</p>

3 Dissemination plan for the second period

This section of the report provides an update of the initial dissemination plan (D4.2) taking into account the results of dissemination activity in period one. The section is designed as a stand-alone document suitable for circulation to the partners' dissemination contacts (who are listed in Annex 2) and communications experts within their organisations.

3.1 Dissemination strategy

ARIADNE is co-funded by the European Commission's Seventh Framework programme and started on the 1st of February 2013; the project runs for four years. It brings together partners from Sweden, UK, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria with relevant expertise, combining excellence in archaeology, informatics and data management, as well as experience in research, innovation policies and international collaboration.

The overall goals of ARIADNE are to:

- integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures, overcoming fragmentation and promoting interoperability, to create a Web of Archaeological Data;
- build a community of researchers around the creation, sharing, use and re-use of archaeological data;
- provide a common access point to distributed archaeological data centres supported by powerful new tools enabling visualization and analysis;
- create a new generation of researchers ready to exploit the research infrastructure by offering training and guidance;
- stimulate new research avenues and innovation in the field of archaeology.

The aim of WP4 (good practices and dissemination) is to develop the consortium's strategy for effective dissemination of the project's results and the research infrastructure in the archaeological community, contributing to a vibrant community of use, and providing best practice guidelines for exploiting the infrastructure within archaeological work.

The aim of the dissemination strategy is to raise awareness about the ARIADNE research infrastructure amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organizations
- Research institutions represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties including deans, directors etc.
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission
- Media and the public at large

This dissemination strategy was prepared by MDR Partners and has been updated by PIN. All partners are involved in project dissemination activities.

The dissemination strategy for the project in period two aims to:

- Build the Stakeholder **contact database** and **following** on social media
- Develop appropriate **materials** targeted to specific audiences
- Coordinate partner activities to maximize **impact**
- Provide qualitative and quantitative **indicators**

For the second dissemination plan period we have identified six main objectives, together with the corresponding activities (Table):

Objective	Description	2014-15 activity
Objective 1	Building the user base for the project website and portal.	Continuing the development of the project website by adding new content to attract users. Disseminating new content widely as it becomes available online. Preparing for the launch of the integrated portal and registries. Informing end users and stakeholders about the availability of new services from the research infrastructure.
Objective 2	Extending the stakeholder database.	Continuing to build the contact database. Developing the project's presence on social networks. Establishing a presence on Mendeley, Academia.edu, Zotero and IAM Researcher. Working with partners to maximize contacts through their networks to disseminate news and build the database.
Objective 3	Informing the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities and transnational access to the infrastructure.	Continuing to post news and information regularly on Twitter and working to increase the following. Producing 4 issues of the Project Newsletter, and disseminating it widely. Increasing the availability of project

		<p>presentations and documents to stakeholders via SlideShare.</p> <p>Use of Mailing lists and Social Networks to disseminate news and drive traffic to the project website.</p> <p>Press Notices – project international conference, launch of integrated portal.</p>
Objective 4	Informing the research community about transnational access and training opportunities.	<p>Preparing the second call to researchers to put forwards proposals for access.</p> <p>Use of dissemination channels to advertise training opportunities to researchers.</p>
Objective 5	Developing the basic set of dissemination materials.	<p>Developing a second edition of the project brochure.</p> <p>Preparing a template for case studies and fact sheets.</p> <p>Providing a second edition of the PowerPoint presentation about the project.</p> <p>Preparing a new Project poster.</p>
Objective 6	Presenting the project at relevant international and national events.	<p>Project presentations at international events.</p> <p>ARIADNE Workshops and conference sessions.</p>

Table: Dissemination strategy

3.2 The stakeholder community

Different approaches are appropriate for different user groups. By developing an understanding of the needs and interests of each group, the project aims to make its dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organizations we hope will be interested in using the research infrastructure, and products such as the Guides to Good practice. Awareness of the needs of the community helps identify the best channels for contacting stakeholder groups (such as email lists, conferences, other means) and in designing and planning dissemination materials and activities, and thus helps raise the visibility of the project.

The ARIADNE stakeholder community includes both direct stakeholders (the envisaged users of the infrastructure and its services) and indirect stakeholders (such as professional associations, policy makers and funding bodies). The initial dissemination plan defined groups of stakeholders (D4.2), these have been updated to reflect work carried out during period one to prepare a “users framework”. This framework distinguished four groups of potentially active direct stakeholders:

- Research projects including lead researchers and project data managers (level 1)
- Institutions including research directors and institutional data/repository managers (level 2)
- Data centres, subject/domain repositories, portals and other online services (level 3)
- Infrastructures and integrated services (level 4)

Other stakeholders who are also important for the project include:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities
- International networks, professional associations and related research infrastructures
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission
- Media and the public at large

3.2.1 Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines

This is the community of researchers, students and field workers active in archaeology research projects with an interest in scientific and technical approaches, and in creating, analyzing, sharing, using and re-using archaeological datasets. This is level one of the ARIADNE user framework, for example, an excavation project with a lead excavator, core team and associated experts. This group can be reached through conferences, events, academic forums and publications. The message should underline the opportunities for using the ARIADNE research infrastructure, openness of data access, tools, innovation and potential new avenues for research.

Researchers are likely to be interested in:

- Data access and datasets; use of repositories and data centres;
- Tools and technologies;
- Forthcoming events, workshops and training opportunities;
- Research quality and innovation.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via scientific conferences and journals, dedicated publications and printed materials, regional and thematic events, training materials and videos etc.

3.2.2 Institutions

Institutions or centres are the umbrellas under which research projects take place. They include both research institutions and heritage management agencies. Research directors oversee and give advice. Many manage an institutional repository where projects can deposit their archives. Amongst archaeological research institutions the emphasis will be on disseminating the potential for advancement in research quality, effectiveness of work and improvements in working practice particularly with regard to depositing and accessing data. The message should underline the advantages for individual institutions and researchers in collaborating with each other and contributing their data.

Managers and senior researchers within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the research infrastructure and its data centres
- Opportunities for collaboration
- Innovation, new tools and services available to researchers
- Forthcoming conferences and events

The primary means of communication with this group will be via dedicated web pages and leaflets, and via regional or thematic events.

Research institutions include universities, archaeological museums, specialist institutes, archaeology schools (such as the foreign archaeology missions based in Cyprus, Rome, Athens, etc.).

3.2.3 Data centres, domain/subject aggregators and service providers

Archaeological data centres have been established in some countries. Subject-based repositories and portals relevant to specialized areas of the archaeology domain are also available. Typically, data centres report the research of many institutions within their country, while most domain/subject repositories are international supporting research specialists from across many countries. The core stakeholders in these centres are the managers of these services. The emphasis will be on disseminating the potential for advancement in the delivery of integrated services, particularly with regard to depositing and accessing data. The messages should underline the advantages for individual centres in collaborating with the ARIADNE research infrastructure.

Managers and senior researchers within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the research infrastructure and its data centres
- Opportunities for collaboration
- Innovation, new tools and services available to researchers
- Forthcoming conferences and events

The primary means of communication with this group will be via dedicated web pages and leaflets, and via regional or thematic events.

3.2.4 Research infrastructures for archaeology

These are research infrastructures active in disciplines related to archaeology or to the work of ARIADNE. This group includes both direct stakeholders (archaeology infrastructures with the potential to benefit from becoming accessible via ARIADNE's integrated services) but has a general interest in infrastructure developments, and there may be opportunities for networking, collaboration and sharing and exchanging news about activities and solutions being developed.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- The development of the infrastructure, tools and services
- Opportunities for collaboration and networking, such as international events
- Business planning and strategy development

The primary means of communication with this group will be via the project leaflet, briefing papers and collaboration events.

3.2.5 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders in ARIADNE partner institutions are one of the target audiences for the ARIADNE project, as it is important to disseminate information to managers and decision makers within partner organizations to raise awareness of the project's activities, and make them aware of opportunities for using the research infrastructure, both for their own members of staff/researchers and for their contacts and networks.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- The development of the infrastructure
- Innovation and the development of tools and methodologies
- Best practices, guidelines and training opportunities
- Data access
- Conferences and other events
- Advancement in research

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make colleagues within the organisation aware of ARIADNE and its activities, to support and promote the development of the research infrastructure and to spread the news by capillary action within individual networks.

Internal stakeholders can be reached during internal meetings, through presentations of the project activities, by distributing dissemination materials and by sharing news.

3.2.6 International networks, professional associations and related research infrastructures

These are international networks, professional associations and research infrastructures active in related disciplines (e.g. DARIAH, CENDARI, Pelagios and others). The organisations within this group are not direct stakeholders within ARIADNE, but have a general interest in infrastructure

developments, and there may be opportunities for networking, collaboration, and sharing and exchanging news about activities and solutions being developed.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- the development of the infrastructure, tools and services;
- opportunities for collaboration and networking, such as international events;
- Business planning and strategy development.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via the project leaflet, briefing papers and collaboration events.

3.2.7 Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies

This group includes policy makers, (for example, from national organizations with responsibilities for research institutions), funding agencies such as bodies with responsibility for funding research on a national level, and the European Commission. The individual representatives of this group typically have broad areas of responsibility, with archaeology being just one of many fields. The main message to this group is around the benefits and positive impact of the research infrastructure on a broad range of stakeholders and end-users.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- Business planning and strategy development;
- The socio-economic impact of the research infrastructure.

The primary means of communication with this group will be via policy briefings, which should be clear and concise for easy access.

3.2.8 Media and the public at large

The public at large are not direct stakeholders of ARIADNE but this group includes individuals with an interest in archaeology, research, and research infrastructures. Opportunities to inform this group about the work and innovations in research through the media and social networks should be exploited, not least because of public influence on policy-makers. Europeana is a potential channel for informing members of the public about ARIADNE and its data centres.

This group is likely to be interested in:

- General information about the project
- Archaeology in general

The methods of communication with this group are the media (TV, radio and press), exhibitions and social networks (Internet, YouTube, Flickr). Dissemination materials include the project website, leaflets, press releases, images and movies.

3.3 Identifying resources

This section identifies the skills and experiences available within the project consortium, and their connections with projects, networks and associations.

3.3.1 Consortium

The best practices and dissemination work package is lead by PIN and involves all partners in the project consortium with support for the web environment from an external sub-contractor, 2Culture Associates Ltd. The ARIADNE consortium consists of partners in 16 countries including Sweden, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria.

All project partners are responsible for contributing to dissemination activities including the identification of events, development of dissemination materials and the project website. Most of the partners have public relations departments in their institutions, or access to external resources, on which to draw relevant skills and experience for disseminating information about ARIADNE.

Responsibilities for dissemination activities:

- The coordinator, PIN and deputy coordinator UoY ADS together have strategic responsibility for coordinating dissemination activities by all partners.
- PIN leads WP4 and is responsible for managing the development of the project website as a one-stop access point to the integrated infrastructure and social network channels.
- PIN with the support of DISCOVERY are responsible for publicising the project and sharing news and information about project results through the project newsletter, social networks and media channels.
- All partners are responsible for publicising the project within their countries via local media and networks, translating dissemination materials into their national language(s) as appropriate.
- DAI and PIN are responsible for coordinating ARIADNE events in the framework of international conferences and all partners offer support as appropriate to the event planning.
- MiBAC-ICCU is responsible for coordinating publication activity.
- UoY-ADS together with KNAW-DANS are responsible for the identification, assessment and definition of good practices with the support of the other “archaeological partners” (DAI, Athena RC, Discovery, ZRC-SAZU, MNM-NOK, CYI-STARC, ARUP-CAS, OAW, NIAM-BAS, MiBAC-ICCI, ARHEO and INRAP) as required.
- UoY-ADS is responsible for coordinating the expansion of the existing online publication of a series of Guides to Good Practice; the project Steering Committee is responsible for approving material for publication; and individual partners are responsible for providing input according to their expertise.
- SRFG, with the support of PIN and UoY-ADS, is responsible for organising the stakeholder survey (in the framework of WP2).
- DISCOVERY, with the support of DAI and Athena-RC, is responsible for coordinating the Special Interest Groups.

3.3.2 External partners and related international initiatives

ARIADNE has entered into cooperation agreements and has established associations with a number of external organisations and international initiatives/projects (section 2.1 above). A number of other organisations, projects, network and research infrastructures have also been identified. Some may enter into formal collaboration agreements with ARIADNE during period two, while others may be interested in following ARIADNE's activities and in cooperating with the project on an informal basis by exchanging news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for ARIADNE will be to make contact with these organisations and initiatives, sharing news about project activities and seeking opportunities for collaboration.

ARIADNE has formal collaborations with:

- CENIEH, Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, Spain
- CNRS-FRANTIQ, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
- IAI-UJA, Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Arqueología Ibérica. Universidad de Jaén, Spain
- IAPH, Archaeological Institute of the Andalusian Heritage, Spain
- MCH- Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo, Norway
- DGPC- Direção-Geral do Património Cultural, Portugal
- Aarhus University, Denmark
- EAGLE project
- DCH-RP
- FAIMS (Federated Archaeological Information Management Systems), Australia
- Digital Antiquity and tDAR (the Digital Archaeological Record), USA.

Other external initiatives which been identified and where there are opportunities for informal cooperation and perhaps formal collaboration include:

- CARARE¹ (community: archaeology and built heritage)
- 3D-ICONS² (community: 3D digitization)
- Europeana³ (community: cultural heritage)
- DARIAH⁴ (: research infrastructure for arts and humanities)
- CENDARI⁵ (: research infrastructure for medieval and modern history)
- EHRI⁶ (community: researchers in holocaust research)
- ArchaeoLandscapes Europe (ArLand), Pelagios, Pleiades, Galia Informations, CSIR (Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani) and European Archaeological Schools abroad (stakeholder community: archaeological research)

¹ <http://www.carare.eu>

² <http://www.3DICONS-project.eu>

³ <http://www.europeana-project.eu>

⁴ <http://www.dariah.eu/>

⁵ <http://www.cendari.eu/>

⁶ <http://www.ehri-project.eu/>

- V-MusT⁷ (stakeholder community: museums)

There is a close relationship between ARIADNE and DARIAH; ARIADNE is an affiliated project within the DARIAH network. The project envisages collaborating with and making use of the services offered by the DARIAH Virtual Competency Centres. The DARIAH Virtual Competency Centre on Advocacy, Impact and Outreach will assist in disseminating ARIADNE results to key influencers in the field.

It is envisaged that ARIADNE will have links with Europeana, which can have impact in stimulating the interest of the broad public audiences in archaeology and heritage, and in stimulating study visits to archaeological museums and sites.

The ARIADNE social networking team (PIN and DISCOVERY) will follow the international projects, initiatives and research infrastructures identified as being of interest via their websites, Twitter feeds and other social network channels.

Partner responsibilities:

- Within the framework of WP2, AIAC will be responsible for coordinating approaches to related international and national initiatives to avoid duplication and increase effect.
- PIN, KNAW-DANS and UoY-ADS coordinates liaising with related EU projects such as DARIAH.
- PIN liaises with the European Projects CARARE, 3D-ICONS, PATHS, LoCloud.
- CNR coordinates liaising with the Europeana foundation.
- Athena RC liaises with DYAS, the planned Arts & Humanities infrastructure for Greece.
- MiBAC-ICCU coordinates liaising with public institutions and liaises with the European projects Athena-Plus, Linked Heritage and DCH-RP.
- AIAC coordinates liaising with Pelagios, Pleiades, Gallia Informations, CSIR and European Archaeological Schools abroad.
- DAI liaises with ArchLand and IANUS.

3.3.3 Groups and associations

Several ARIADNE partners are members of groups and associations active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information to their stakeholders. The strategy for ARIADNE will be to explore opportunities to disseminate news and information about project activities with these groups.

The groups and associations that have been identified include:

- European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)
- Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) – contact = Cesar Gonzalez-Perez (CSIC) is CAA Membership Secretary
- VAST – contacts = Franco Niccolucci (PIN) - General Co-Chair and Achille Felicetti - International Program Committee

⁷ <http://www.v-must.net/>

- Digisam Sweden – a network for coordination of digitization, digital preservation and digital access to cultural heritage in Sweden – contact = Ulf Jakobsson, SND
- Association of Cypriot Archaeologists (ACA) contact = Sorin Hermon, STARC
- Society of Cypriot Studies = Sorin Hermon, STARC
- Historic Environment Information Resources Network (HIERNET) Julian Richards, ADS
- Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH) Julian Richards, ADS

3.3.4 Community building

Community building is fostered through the activities of WP2, which during period two will include:

- Disseminating the results of the initial survey of user needs to the stakeholders who took part in the survey and to the wider community by publishing papers, sharing news, etc.
- Identifying lead users who are willing to participate in focus groups (or a user panel) to follow-up to the initial survey of user needs and to contribute to the development of the ARIADNE infrastructure by providing feedback on developments.
- Inviting stakeholders to take part in a second online survey to follow up the initial findings on user needs.
- Continuing to support the Special Interest Groups (SIGs) in the research community with the aim of discussing the state of the art and issues relating to the creation and use of datasets. The individual SIGS will meet during the period (normally during existing conferences) and will continue to discuss and report on their areas. The SIGs are:
 - 3D and Visualisation
 - Archaeological Research Practices and Methods
 - Remote Sensing and Spatial Data
 - Scientific Data
 - Excavation and Monument Data
 - Grey Literature
 - Linked Data
 - Metadata and Semantics
- Publication of position papers by SIGs.
- Making use of online and social networking tools for discussion, to share news, calls for participation and information about resources made available on the project website.

3.3.5 Contact database

The objective for 2014-15 will be to continue to build the project's contact database by encouraging subscriptions to the project website and newsletter, followers on Twitter and membership of the project's LinkedIn group. Accounts will be established for the project in Mendeley, Academia.edu, Zotero and IAM Researcher, which are used by the academic community.

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include community building activities such as carrying out the Stakeholder Survey and developing Special Interest Groups, as well as liaising with research institutions, related international and national initiatives, cooperation with groups and associations, disseminating news and updates about the project's activities through

various channels including direct contacts of partners' network, use of social media, project newsletter, partners' newsletters, press notices and by participating in conferences and events.

3.4 Informing the stakeholder community

The objective is to inform the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities, the development of the infrastructure and the availability of datasets, tools and services. This will be done through the different channels (project newsletter, mailing lists, social networks, press notices) documented below, as well as via project events, workshops, tutorials and other activities.

Our strategy is to make the initial approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

Contacts will be made through the use of an appropriate **message** to transmit information, which should vary according to the target audience. For example, when reaching the research community we could point out specific publications on the project website, news about forthcoming conferences or innovation in the archaeological research infrastructure.

During 2014-15 the editorial strategy for the project newsletter and news disseminated via the social networks will be to:

- Share news about developments in the ARIADNE infrastructure, project activities and achievements
- Promote Calls for Participation in ARIADNE workshops, training events and TNA summer schools
- Promote access to ARIADNE TNA online services and the integrated portal
- Share news about events organized by the project
- Share news from affiliated organisations and projects
- Share news from related research infrastructures and initiatives active in same area as ARIADNE
- Promote open sharing of data
- Share news about developments in the state-of-the art
- Share news from ARIADNE (and related) special interest groups
- Share news about opportunities and benefits for researchers and research projects

3.4.1 News on the project website

Short articles will continue to be published on the project website, alongside calls for papers and participation in events. News will continue to be disseminated via Twitter (see below) with the project tweet feed being published on the home page of the project website.

3.4.2 Project newsletter

The editorial strategy for the project newsletter during 2014-15 will be to create articles discussing ARIADNE-related topics. A short version of the newsletter will be prepared for email distribution; this will continue to contain short excerpts linked to full news stories published on the project website. The aim of this approach is to drive traffic to the project website.

Four issues of the newsletter are planned during period two of the project. These will be distributed directly to stakeholders registered on our mailing lists, indirectly to email lists, and via notices on the social networks. The full newsletter will be available on the project website.

3.4.3 Social networks

Twitter - Ariadne_Network

The strategy for **Twitter**⁸ during 2014-15 will be to:

- Post tweets related to the project's activities (newsletter, events, project progress) or information related to domains of interest to ARIADNE and its Special Interest Groups. This will keep followers informed about the project and activate new discussions around pertinent areas.
- Encourage partners to share interesting news, and then tweet about it with the project hashtag #Ariadne_Network.
- Monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag.
- Involve ARIADNE project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around ARIADNE by tweeting about the project (@Ariadne_Network) and retweeting any tweets of interest.
- Include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website.
- Integrate Twitter with LinkedIn and Facebook. Tweets will be automatically re-posted onto LinkedIn and Facebook: this mechanism will ensure a consistent flow of information and will populate the social networks.
- Follow relevant Twitter users. This activity gives the ARIADNE project visibility: some of these users might follow ARIADNE in return or retweet project tweets to their followers etc.

Partners will continue to be encouraged to tweet about ARIADNE in their national languages mentioning the project using @Ariadne_Network to enable retweeting.

LinkedIn

The strategy for **LinkedIn** during 2014-15 will be to promote discussion about ARIADNE and to support the Special Interest Groups and their discussions. The objective will be to increase the number of followers of the group(s) during the year.

A group has been established for ARIADNE at:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4966050&trk=anet_ug_hm

Among the list of relevant existing LinkedIn groups we identified:

- ArchaeoLandscapes Europe (ArcLand)
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage Group
- CAA: Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology
- CARARE: connecting archaeology and architecture to Europeana
- CIDOC - International Documentation Committee of ICOM

⁸ <http://www.twitter.com/3Dicons>

- Computer Vision Technologies
- Digital Heritage Preservation
- Geomatics
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage
- Laser Scanning
- Laser Scanning Forum
- The LiDAR Forum
- Open Source LiDAR
- Photogrammetry & Laser Scanning
- Spatial Ireland
- Web3D Professionals
- WebGL Developers

Slideshare

A Slideshare account has been established for the project: ariadnenetwork. The strategy for 2014-15 will be to increase the availability of project presentations, reports and other publications available to users of Slideshare.

YouTube

A **YouTube** channel has been established for the project. To date this channel has been used to upload a single video. The strategy for 2014-15 will be to evaluate the potential to produce further videos suitable for uploading to this channel.

Other media channels

- Flickr – this will be used to share photos of project events
- Mendeley
- Academia.edu
- Zotero
- IAM Researcher
- Partner’s websites
- Partner’s newsletters, blogs and news feeds

3.4.4 External Newsletters

Other newsletters which may take ARIADNE news, stories or short articles include magazines and newsletters produced by partners, affiliates, related initiatives and news organisations. Some possible publications are listed below.

Title	Description	Deadline
AIAC news	The newsletter of the International Association of Classical Archaeology http://www.aiac.org/en/aiacnews	3 issues per year
The European	The newsletter of the European Association of Archaeologists	2 issues per

Archaeologist	http://e-a-a.org/tea/	year
ADS News	The newsletter of the Archaeology Data Service http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/newsletter	1 issue per year
DANS news	www.dans.knaw.nl/en/content/news	Regular updates
GARR news	http://www.garrnews.it/ in Italian	Annual

3.4.5 Mailing lists

The members of the project team are each registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different aspects of archaeological research, including specialist subject areas, uses of particular technologies, digital preservation, general topics in cultural heritage and digital libraries and business domains. Although many people subscribe to more than one mailing list, the full membership of each list differs.

The project is creating a document summarising relevant email lists. To avoid multiple postings team members will be asked to take responsibility for circulating project news to specified mailing lists. Partners have been asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A master list will then be made to enable the dissemination of news items to the lists to be coordinated by PIN with support from all partners.

The strategy is to post notices about ARIADNE to the lists (for example to announce a new issue of the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the website and allow contacts the opportunity of registering on the website as users.

The work of sending notices will be done periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The emailing lists which have been identified include:

- ARCH-AC-UK - UK academic archaeologists mailing list: <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=ARCH-AC-UK>
- ROSA - Slovenian archaeologists mailing list (ZRC SAZU)
- Musei-IT
- Associazione nazionale archeologi
- antiquist@googlegroups.com
- ADS News (ADS)
- Datalink (DANS newsletter) (KNAW-DANS)
- International Association for Classical Archaeology (AIAC's list)
- Society of Cypriot Studies (STARC)
- Association of Cypriot Archaeologists (STARC)
- Archaeological Research Unit-University of Cyprus (STARC)

- New Archaeological Research Network for Integrating Approaches to Ancient Material Studies- (NARNIA) - (STARC)

3.4.6 Press notices

Press notices and press releases are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: newspapers or magazines (online or paper versions), news sites, news networks.

A press release will be prepared to announce the international project workshop being held in Rome in November 2014 under the Italian Presidency of the EU.

A press section has been established on the project website as an information point for members of media organisations at: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/Press>.

3.5 Dissemination materials

A set of dissemination materials has been produced for the project and this will be maintained and developed during period two. The dissemination materials include:

3.5.1 Project website

The ARIADNE website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) will continue to be maintained and developed by the addition of new content during period two. The aim of the site continues to be to provide information about the project and its activities to stakeholders, news, calls for participation, resources and services (including access to the ARIADNE integrated portal, which will provide a single point of access to the research infrastructure).

The public-facing parts of the website include:

- About – the project, consortium and activities
- Events calendar
- Services – transnational access and training
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- News – news stories, bulletins and newsletter
- Contacts

The website was initially made available in English. The project plans to make information pages available for stakeholders in other community languages during the period.

3.5.2 Project leaflet

MiBACT-ICCU, with support from PIN, will coordinate the preparation of a second version of the project leaflet, to present the project and its main activities, and be made available for distribution by partners at events.

The need for a more detailed brochure will be investigated.

3.5.3 Other dissemination materials

The basic set of promotional materials will be updated as appropriate during period two. The materials include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners
- A set of project logos for use in printed materials and online resources, with branding guidelines and instructions for printers
- Templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.
- A project brochure
- A project poster
- An ARIADNE essentials PowerPoint presentation

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the Intranet of the ARIADNE project website. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by partners.

3.5.4 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag logo.

Example: "ARIADNE is a project funded by the European Commission under the Community's Seventh Framework Programme, contract no. FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1-313193".

Any communication or publication shall state that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

3.6 Dissemination activities

3.6.1 Events

This activity concerns participation by project partners in events including:

- single project presentation at conferences or symposia
- dedicated project sessions
- workshops
- tutorials or short training sessions
- participation in exhibitions with a booth, poster or demo

3.6.1.1 ARIADNE at international events

DAI and PIN manage the logistics of project events taking place in the framework of larger events including contacts with the organisers, arrangements for participation, payment of fees and so on. PIN and UoY ADS together guarantee to provide a project presence at key events.

During 2014, ICCU with the support of PIN, is organizing an international conference workshop in Rome on the topic of “**Research Infrastructure and e-Infrastructures for Digital Cultural Heritage**”. The workshop will take place in Rome on 13-14 November and is an official event of the Italian Presidency of the European Union. The programme will include speakers from the European Commission, Research Infrastructures and professional associations directed towards an audience of senior policy makers. A series of dissemination activities are planned around the conference.

During period two, ARIADNE plans to organize workshops, to deliver training and to give presentations at international conferences. The conferences where ARIADNE may organize its own events include:

- The yearly European Archaeologists Association (EAA) conference with an audience of around 1,000 archaeological delegates;
- The yearly Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA) conference with an audience of around 400 delegates focused on IT in archaeology;
- The yearly VAST conference, on IT applications in archaeology, with a more technical audience of around 100 attendees;
- The EVA conference series regularly organized in various locations (Florence, London, Jerusalem, Moscow, etc.) and an audience of cultural heritage practitioners and researchers.

The project’s presence at such events may include workshops, sessions, individual presentations, posters etc. The aim will be to disseminate the project’s activities and promote the opportunities offered by the research infrastructure to researchers and in particular to young researchers.

A set of dissemination materials will be prepared each year for use in international events. These will be made available online in English for translation into local languages as appropriate.

International Events

A series of international events have been identified which are of interest to ARIADNE's stakeholders and potential opportunities for project presentations.

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
CIDOC 2014 http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/	Annual conference of CIDOC: Access and Understanding – Networking in the Digital Era	Dresden, Germany	6-11 Sept 2014
PECSRL 2014 http://www.pecsrl2014.com/index.html	"Unraveling the Logics of Landscape"	Gothenberg and Mariestad, Sweden	8-12 Sept 2014
Digital Libraries 2014 http://www.dl2014.org/	Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL) and International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2014)	London, UK	8-12 Sept 2014
EHRI workshop http://www.ehri-project.eu/ehri-agenda-2014	EHRI Interdisciplinary Workshop on Physical and Digital Preservation	Jerusalem, Israel	8-10 Sept 2014
NKOS workshop 2014	13 th European NKOS workshop, held at Digital Libraries 2014	London, UK	11-12 Sept 2014
EAA 2014 https://www.eaa2014istanbul.org/paket	20 th Annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists	Istanbul, Turkey	10-14 Sept, 2014
EAA: Open Access session	"Barriers and Opportunities: Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology" https://www.eaa2014istanbul.org/sayfa/139	Istanbul, Turkey	13 Sept, 2014
LAC 2014 http://www.let.vu.nl/en/research/conferences/lac-2014/index.asp	3 rd International Landscape Archaeology Conference	Rome, Italy	17-20 Sept 2014
DARIAH VCC meeting http://dariah.eu/activities/general-vcc-meetings/4th-general-vcc-meeting/programme.html	DARIAH-EU: 4 th general Virtual Competence Centres meeting	Rome, Italy	17-19 Sept 2014
AARG 2014 http://www.aarg2014.org/	Annual meeting of the Aerial Archaeology Research Group	Dublin, Ireland	24-26 Sept 2014
VAST http://www.vast2014.eu/home-en/	14 th International symposium on virtual reality, archaeology and cultural heritage: "Virtual Research Environment for Cultural Heritage"	Pistoia, Italy	Postponed to December 2014

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
GCH 2014 http://diglib.eg.org/GCH2014	12 th Eurographics workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage	Darmstadt, Germany	6-8 th Oct 2014
iPRES 2014	11 th International Conference on Digital Preservation	Melbourne, Australia	6-10 Oct 2014
Girona 2014 http://www.girona.cat/web/ica2014/eng/index.php	Archives and Cultural Industries event grouping together the Annual conference of the International Council on Archives, the 9 th European Conference on Archives and the 13 th Image and Research Seminar	Girona, Spain	13-15 Oct 2014
EHRI workshop http://www.ehri-project.eu/ehri-agenda-2014	EHRI workshop	Budapest, Hungary	14 Oct 2014
Arqueologica 2.0 http://www.arqueologiavirtual.com/seav/	6 th International meeting on Graphic Archaeology and Informatics	Ciudad Real, Spain	15-17 Oct 2014
EuroMed 2014	5 th EuroMed Conference International workshop on Big Data in Digital Cultural Heritage	Limassol, Cyprus	3-8 Nov 2014
CHNT 19 http://www.stadtarchaeologie.at/	Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies: Urban Archaeology and Processing	Vienna, Austria	3-5 Nov 2014
MTR 2014 http://www.mtr-conf.org/	8 th Metadata and Semantics Research Conference	Karlsruhe, Germany	27-29 Nov 2014
CIDOC CRM SIG	CIDOC CRM Special Interest Group meeting with the IFLA FRBR review group	Stockholm, Sweden	9-12 Feb 2015
ArcLand Final Conference http://www.d1319503-42371.cp.blacknight.com/arcland.eu/index.php/outrreach/conferences/1783-sensing-the-past-new-approaches-to-european-landscapes-rcland-final-conference-2015	The final conference of the <i>ArcLand</i> project "Sensing the Past — New Approaches to European Landscapes"	Frankfurt, Germany	24-26 Feb 2015
CAA 2015, http://caa-international.org/	Annual international conference CSIC-INCIPIT intends to propose a workshop on "Hands-on Archaeological Conceptual Modelling" and a session on "Methodologies of archaeological practice"	Siena, Italy	30 March – 4 April 2015

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
ICRPA 2015	International Colloquium on Roman Provincial Art	Dijon, France	31 May – 7 Jun 2015
PATCH 2015	International Workshop on Personalized Access to Cultural Heritage	To be confirmed	Feb 2015
EVA http://www.eva-conferences.com/	EVA Florence 2015	Florence, Italy	May 2015
	EVA London 2015	London, UK	July 2015
iPRES 2015 http://ipres-conference.org/	12 th International Conference on Digital Preservation	Chapel Hill, North Carolina, USA	20-23 Oct 2015
EAA 2015 http://e-a-a.org/conferences.htm#future	21 st Annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists	Glasgow, Scotland	2-6 September, 2015
JCDL 2015 http://www.jcdl.org/	Joint Conference on Digital Libraries	To be confirmed	Sept 2015
EMAC 2015 http://www.archaiologia.gr/en/blog/2014/07/28/emac-2015-%E2%80%90-13th-european-meeting-on-ancient-ceramics/	13th European Meeting on Ancient Ceramics	Athens, Greece	24-26 September 2015
Digital Heritage 2015	2 nd edition of Digital Heritage, the conference first held in Marseilles in 2013 which combined VSMM2013 (Virtual Systems and Multimedia), GCH2013 (Eurographics Symposium on Graphics and Cultural Heritage), Memory of the World (UNESCO) with a series of events and workshops	To be confirmed	Oct – Nov 2015
ICDH 2015 http://www.waset.org/conference/2015/11/london/ICDH	International Conference on Digital Heritage	London, UK	27-28 2015
CHNT 20 http://www.stadtarchaeologie.at	Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies: Public Relations	Vienna, Austria	TBC November 2015
MTSR 2015	9 th Metadata and Semantics Research Conference	To be confirmed	TBC Nov 2015
EAA 2016 http://e-a-a.org/conferences.htm	22 nd Annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists	Vilnius, Lithuania	30 Aug – 4 Sept 2016
iPRES 2016 http://ipres-conference.org/	13 th International Conference on Digital Preservation	Bern, Switzerland	3-7 Oct 2016

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
EAA 2017 http://e-a-a.org/conferences.htm	23 rd Annual meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists	Maastricht, Netherlands	3 Sept 2017

Potential National events

During 2014-15 ARIADNE was presented by partners at a number of national events. Some events coming up on national level during 2014-15 are listed below:

Conference	Description	Location	Dates
CAA	CAA national chapters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAA-UK • CAA-Germany • CAA-Netherlands • CAA-Estonia • CAA-Greece • CAA-Norway • CAA-Poland • CAA-Sweden 	Various	various
DHBenelux conference http://dhbenelux.org/	A yearly event to promote Digital Humanities research in Belgium, Luxembourg and the Netherlands	Antwerp, Netherlands	11-12 June 2014
DARIAH-GR	DARIAH- GR launched in June 2014 with a two-day conference and workshop on the objectives of the Greek research infrastructure.	Athens, Greece	Annual?
Cyprus Institute	Virtual Heritage School on Digital Cultural Heritage	Nicosia, Cyprus	Annual
Lange Nacht der Forschung'	Science night	Austria	Annual
Borsa mediterranea del turismo archeologico	http://www.borsaturismo.com/	Paestum, Italy	Annual, November
Digital Heritage	Annual conference hosted by the Centre for Digital Heritage	York, UK	Annual, July
Danube Limes Brand	Annual project conference: UNESCO World Heritage in the Lower Danube	To be confirmed	Annual, June-July

3.6.2 Publications

Scientific publications by partners concerning project work in academic journals will continue to be encouraged. Standard academic good practice concerning citation of authors is anticipated with the proviso that authors should:

- a) mention EU support for the work;

- b) notify the consortium of the publication;
- c) provide a digital copy to the consortium, to be made available on the website (if the publisher agrees with the Open Access Self-Archiving initiative www.eprints.org/openaccess/) or a link provided to an archive copy elsewhere; or to be kept in storage, if self-archiving is not allowed.

In addition to scientific publications, we anticipate that during period two the project will publish:

- Training materials
- Service specific brochures and fact sheets
- An updated project brochure

MiBAC-ICCU coordinates this task and, with support from PIN and UoY-ADS, will establish an editorial committee for project publications such as reports, training materials and other literature. The membership of the committee will be convened from the project partnership or external experts as appropriate to the publication.

Material published by the project will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial licence. Publications will be available for download from the web site with printed materials being produced for distribution at events etc. Copies of project publications will be uploaded to the ARIADNE SlideShare account where possible.

3.6.2.1 Potential journals

Potential journals for publication of articles by project partners have been identified below.

Journal	Description	Deadline
Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage	ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH) publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the innovative use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage. We encourage the submission of manuscripts that demonstrate innovative use of technology for the discovery, analysis, interpretation and presentation of findings as well as manuscripts that illustrate applications in the Cultural Heritage sector that challenge the computational technologies and suggest new research opportunities in computer science. http://jocch.acm.org/	Quarterly
Archeomatica	A new, multidisciplinary journal, printed in Italy, devoted to the presentation and the dissemination of advanced Methodologies, techniques and emerging technologies for the knowledge, documentation, exploitation and conservation of cultural heritage. http://www.archeomatica.it/	Quarterly
Journal of Cultural Heritage	A Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology for Conservation and Awareness. The Journal of Cultural Heritage is devoted to: - Safeguarding, Conservation and exploitation of cultural heritage - Analyses and preservation of biodiversity - Sociological and economical analyses - Computer sciences in Cultural heritage	6 issues a year

	http://www.elsevier.com/wps/find/journaldescription.cws_home/620738/description#description	
International Journal of Heritage in Digital Era	The International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE) is a quarterly high quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries. http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	Quarterly
Archaeometry Workshop	e-journal http://www.ace.hu/am/indexe.html	
Hungarian Archaeology	e-journal http://www.hungarianarchaeology.hu/	
Digitalia	Digitalia: rivista del digitale nei beni culturali Digital and printes Journal on digital cultural heritage, containing articles, projects, events, reviews, edited by ICCU http://digitalia.sbn.it/ in Italian	Annual
Archeologia e Calcolatori	Since 1990 Archeologia e Calcolatori has been an international observatory of theoretical and methodological aspects of computing and information technology applied to archaeology. http://soi.cnr.it/archcalc/ edited by CNR In Italian	Annual
International Journal of Spatial Data Infrastructures Research	http://ijsdir.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	Annual

3.6.3 Guides to Good Practice

UoY-ADS is responsible for managing the expansion of the existing online publication of Guides to Good Practice relevant to the ARIADNE infrastructure. Work planned for period two includes:

- Publication of new guidelines for:
 - 3D Datasets
 - Dendrochronology and Scientific Analysis
- Publication of new case studies applying good practices to datasets held by ARIADNE partners
- Cross-referencing of existing guidelines held by ADS, DANS and DAI
- Collaboration with the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D ICONS projects to align and reference their forthcoming publications with those in preparation by ARIADNE

Electronic copies of the Guides will be published under a Creative Commons Attribution, Share-Alike, Non-Commercial licence. The Guides will be published on the ADS website as part of the existing series; a page will be created on the ARIADNE site where details of the guides and links to the content can be made available to ARIADNE users.

ARIADNE information leaflets featuring the Guides will be made available for distribution.

News about the preparation and publication of the Guides and case studies by ARIADNE and related publications by the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D ICONS projects will be disseminated via project news channels.

3.7 Transnational Access and Training

During the second project period there will continue to be dissemination activity to support the promotion of the transnational access and training being offered by ARIADNE.

3.7.1 Physical access

Calls for participation for physical access to the ARIADNE infrastructure, including summer schools and other access will be advertised in winter-spring 2014 and winter-spring 2015.

PIN, supported by UoY-ADS, will lead the promotion of calls to invite European researchers to participate in physical access to the facilities at PIN, Athena Research Centre and CNR. Calls will be advertised on the project website and disseminated internationally via the social media and news channels described above.

PIN, with the support of UoY-ADS, Athena Research Centre and CNR, will convene meetings of the User Selection Panel to assist in the process of reviewing applications for physical access.

News about summer schools and access visits will be disseminated through ARIADNE news channels. Researchers who receive ARIADNE funding will be invited to share news about their experiences and results.

3.7.2 Online Access

Integrated access to the ARIADNE online services will be launched during period two. PIN, with the support of UoY-ADS, DAI, AIAC, DANS and all content partners will promote access to the online services. A series of news stories will be planned and released via the project newsletter, website and news channels.

3.7.3 Training

UoY-ADS leads this task with the support of PIN, DAI, Athena RC, CNR and AIAC. A series of activities are planned relating to the training of researchers in the use of the infrastructure portal. This includes a series of training workshops to be held during international conferences, which in 2014-15 includes:

- EAA Istanbul 2014 (12-14 September 2014) (confirmed)
- BMTA: Mediterranean Exchange of Archaeological Tourism, Paestum (30-31 October – 1-2 November 2014)
- CAA Siena (April 2015)
- EAA Glasgow (September 2015)

These training workshops provide opportunities to disseminate news and information about ARIADNE and its services to participants. A set of information leaflets will be prepared for distribution during the training workshops.

Calls for participation and news from the training workshops will be disseminated via ARIADNE news channels and the social media.

Training materials and information leaflets will be made available on the ARIADNE website and via SlideShare, and their availability will be disseminated to researchers via the news channels.

3.8 Monitoring and evaluation

The dissemination programme will be monitored and evaluated to review:

- what messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them
- whether those messages are being understood and remembered, and
- whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.

This information will help in planning subsequent phases of the marketing strategy, in developing future marketing activities and to revisions of this marketing strategy plan. It will ensure that the marketing strategy is effectively reaching the target audiences, and they are taking action on the messages they receive.

Success indicators:

Description		Month 18	Month 36	Month 48
Stakeholder involvement	No of institutions	50	75	100
User involvement	No of participants	75 ⁹	1500	2000
Project website	Visitors	6000	9000	12000
Research infrastructure online services	Anonymous users		400	800
Research infrastructure online services	Registered users		400	600

⁹ 772 users participated during period one; the targets for periods two and three have been increased to take this into account

Social networks	No of members	500	1000	1500
Presentations at international events	No. of participants	1000	2000	3000
Good practice guides accessed	No. of unique visitors	100	1000	1500
Newsletters	Readers	100	150	300

The following statistics are available for the project website and products such as the Guides to Good Practice:

- Page views
- Unique visitors
- Return visitors
- Visits
- Amount of time spent on the site/bounce rate
- Visitor's country
- Referral data (search terms)

4 Conclusion

This deliverable presents a progress report on dissemination activities during the first eighteen months of the ARIADNE project, referenced against the initial dissemination plan (D4.2), and provides an update to the dissemination plan presenting our strategy for the period from August 2014 to 31 December 2015 (months eighteen to thirty-six of the ARIADNE project).

In the first year, dissemination activities focused on raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts, building the stakeholder community, and the launch of transnational access. Period two will see the launch of ARIADNE integrated services, and dissemination activities will aim to raise awareness and increase the use of ARIADNE services.

This dissemination plan will be updated at month 36 in preparation for the third project phase.

5 References

1. Annex I – “Description of Work”-DoW
2. ARIADNE website: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu
3. ARIADNE, 2013, D4.1 ARIADNE website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>
4. ARIADNE, 2013, D4.2 ARIADNE initial dissemination plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>
5. ARIADNE, 2014, First report on users’ needs: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

Annex 1: Contact people

Each partner has been requested to identify a contact person responsible for disseminating and sharing news and information channels relevant for ARIADNE.

Partner	Contact person	Email
PIN	Stephanie Williams Csenge Kosztolanyi Kate Fernie Sheena Basset	stephanie.williams@pin.unifi.it csenge.kosztolanyi@pin.unifi.it kfernie27@gmail.com sheena.giess@gmail.com
University of York	Julian Richards Holly Wright	julian.richards@york.ac.uk holly.wright@york.ac.uk
KNAW-DANS	Hella Hollander	hella.hollander@dans.knaw.nl
Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (DAI)	Ruth Beusing	beusing@web.de
Athena Research Centre - CETI	Christos Chamzas	chamzas@ceti.gr
Athena Research Centre - DCU	Agiati Benardou	a.benardou@dcu.gr
CNR ISTI (NeMIS + VCLab)	Carlo Meghini	carlo.meghini@isti.cnr.it
CNR ITABC	Augusto Palombini	augusto.palombini@itabc.cnr.it
Salzburg Research (SFRG)	Guntram Geser	guntram.geser@salzburgresearch.at
Discovery Programme	Anthony Corns	Anthony@discoveryprogramme.ie
Goeteborgs Universitet (Swedish National Data Service, SND)	Ulf Jakobsson	ulf.jakobsson@snd.gu.se
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)	Cesar Gonzalez-Perez	cesar.gonzalez-perez@incipit.csic.es
Znanstvenoraziskovalni Center Slovenske Akademije Znanosti in Umetnosti (ZRC-SAZU)	Benjamin STULAR, Mateja BELAK	bstular@zrc-sazu.si , mateja@zrc-sazu.si
University of Glamorgan	Douglas Tudhope	dstudhope@glam.ac.uk
Magyar Nemzeti Múzeum	Attila Kreiter, Eszter Kreiter	attila.kreiter@mnm-nok.gov.hu , eszter.kreiter@mnm-nok.gov.hu
Cyprus Institute (CYI-STARC)	Sorin Hermon	s.hermon@cyi.ac.cy
Foundation for Research and	Maria Theodoridou	maria@ics.forth.gr

Technology Hellas (FORTH)		
Archeologicky Ustav Av Cr Praha VII (ARUP-CAS)	Dana Krivankova	krivankova@arup.cas.cz
Oesterreichische Akademie Der Wissenschaften (OEAW)	Edeltraud Aspöck	edeltraud.aspoeck@oeaw.ac.at
Associazione Internazionale di Archeologia Classica Onlus (AIAC)	Elizabeth Fentress	elizabeth.fentress@gmail.com
National Institute of Archaeology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Science (NIAM-BAS)	Nadezhda Kecheva	n.kecheva@gmail.com
Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico delle biblioteche italiane e per le informazioni bibliografiche (MIBAC-ICCU)	Maria Teresa Natale Sara Di Giorgio	mariateresa.natale@gmail.com sara.digiorgio@beniculturali.it
Asociatia Arheo Vest (ARHEO)	Simona Simionescu	arheovest@gmail.com
Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventives (INRAP)	Amala Marx	amala.marx@inrap.fr
Universiteit Leiden (LU)	Milco Wansleeben	m.wansleeben@arch.leidenuniv.nl

Annex 2: List of dissemination activities in period one

Events where ARIADNE Dissemination Materials have been distributed/displayed

Date	Place and Country	Event + URL of website	Note	Partner
February 2013				
18	Rome	Workshop with National heads of the Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani, to create a unified digital dataset of sculpture. DAI, Rome.		DAI AIAC
March 2013				
22	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Arheologija v letu 2013 - dediščina za javnost (Archaeology in 2013 - heritage for the public) http://arheoportalsi.si/predavanja/arheologija-v-letu-2013---dediscina-za-javnost	Presentation of ARIADNE project	ZRC SAZU
25-28	Perth, Australia	CAA 2013, www.caa2013.org	Session "Archaeological Information Modelling" and Workshop "Hands-On Archaeological Conceptual Modelling" (CSIC)	CSIC
25-28	Perth, Australia	CAA 2013 www.caa2013.org	ARIADNE project poster	Discovery, UoY-ADS
April 2013				
	Groningen, The Netherlands	SOJA conference (Symposium Onderzoek Jonge Archeologen)	Flyer handed out to 150 starting/young archaeologists -- http://www.dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/Uitgaven/Flyers/folder%20EDNA%20DEFWEB.pdf	KNAW-DANS
08-10	Porto, Portugal	ECLAP 2013, 2nd International Conference on Information Technologies for Performing Arts, Media Access and Entertainment http://www.eclap.eu/drupal/?q=node/113965	Presented paper-ARIADNE: "Validating the Digital Documentation of Cultural Objects"	PIN

22-24	Siena, Italy	Mind the Gap - international seminar http://thelrc.wordpress.com/2013/02/22/mind-the-gap-an-international-seminar-on-emptiness-visibility-ambiguity-and-absence-in-archaeology/	ARIADNE - materials	DAI
May 2013				
6	Xi'an, China	Sustainable Archaeology	Presentation: 'Digital Data in archaeology: long term preservation and access'	UoY-ADS
13-17	Merida	CIAC congress http://aiac2013merida-mnar.icac.net/	ARIADNE presentation	AIAC
23-24	Rome, Italy	Il SITAR nella Rete della Ricerca Italiana Verso la conoscenza archeologica condivisa- Terzo Convegno http://www.garr.it/a/eventi/eventi-comunita/details/94-convegno-sitar-2013 .	Presentation of ARIADNE project c.50 participants	PIN
27-30	Nicosia, Cyprus	Virtual Heritage School on Digital Cultural Heritage, Nicosia	Presentation of ARIADNE project C. 20 young archaeologists	PIN, CYI-STARC
28	Bristol, UK	UK & Irish Isotopes Group Workshop	ARIADNE - Scientific data integration/ Coordination with national initiatives	DISCOVERY
29-2 June	Vienna, Austria	10th International Conference on Archaeological Prospection, Austrian Academy of Sciences, http://ap2013.univie.ac.at/	ARIADNE poster & materials	OEAW
31	Hissar, Bulgaria	LII National Archaeological Conference, May 28-31, 2013 http://naim.bg/bg/content/news/600/EAA conference 857/357/	ARIADNE announced as a part of the progress of AIS AKB in 2013 (by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov)	NIAM-BAS
June 2013				

3-7	Stockholm, Sweden	CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting	Proposal: integration of a part of CRMgeo (which is part of the ARIADNE Global Model) to the CIDOC-CRM core classes.	FORTH
13-15	Pisa	MAPPA final conference: Opening the Past http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/?page_id=136&lang=en	Keynote speech on Open Archaeology. Paper presented by KNAW-DANS. c. 75 archaeologists	UoY-ADS and KNAW-DANS
13-15	Pisa	Mappa Project, final conference: Opening the Past 2013 Archaeology of the Future, in MapPapers 1-III, 2013, pp. 42-43 MapPapers 1-III	Lecture and paper: Past the Opening: building towards the present, on-going dissemination of Dutch archaeological data as part of the DANS archive.	KNAW- DANS
July 2013				
5	Marburg	Colloquium: Hessian Department of Archaeology	ARIADNE - materials	DAI
6	York, UK	Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past http://www.york.ac.uk/digital-heritage/events/cdh-2013/	ARIADNE poster	UoY-ADS Discovery
22-26	Indianapolis, Indiana, USA	JCDL 2013 www.jcdl2013.org	Disseminate news about ARIADNE	Athena RC
September 2013				
2-5	Lisbon, Portugal	iPRES 2013 http://ipres2013.ist.utl.pt/	Paper: Preservation Aspects of a Curation-Oriented Thematic Aggregator	Athena RC
4	Pilsen, Czech Republic	Data Management Planning and Online Resources for Archaeology Workshop http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/ARIADNE-Workshop-EAA-2013	ARIADNE training workshop on data management planning and transnational access c. 25 researchers	UoY-ADS, SRFG, SND, KNAW-DANS, DAI, AIAC

4-7	Pilsen, Czech Republic	EAA conference session, "New digital developments in heritage Management and research " http://proposal.eaa2013.cz/programme/session-abstract.php?id=9	Conference session included introductions to ARIADNE c. 70 archaeologists	UoY-ADS and PIN
4-7	Pilsen	EAA 2013, in the Session "Towards a real representation and interpretation of spatio-temporal data in Archaeological Record"	Paper "An ontological spatio-temporal refinement for the CIDOC CRM and GIS standards"	FORTH
6	Copenhagen	DARIAH VCC meeting	ARIADNE update presentation	PIN
17	Weimar, Germany	3D PITOTI Workshop www.pitoti.org	ARIADNE – distribution of materials	DAI
19-21	Padova, Italy	12th European Meeting on Ancient Ceramics (EMAC2013)	Disseminate news about ARIADNE to the archaeometry community	CSIC
20 - 26	Pontignano, Siena, Italy	International Summer School "Drones applied to Cultural Heritage and Archaeology" http://www.archeomatica.it/images/images/UAVsummerchool2013.pdf	Introduction of ARIADNE to participants	CNR ITABC
20	Cottbus, Germany	KickOff Event of DFG project "OpenInfRA"	ARIADNE presentation to possible partners	DAI
24-25	Amersfoort, Netherlands	ArLand plenary meeting 2013 https://www.surveymonkey.com/s.aspx?sm=_2bpsEmpZ_2bqRFSKx_2fat8Fnig_3d_3d	Participation by ARIADNE partners; networking and collaboration opportunity	ARUP CAS, Discovery
25	Zeist, The Netherlands	SIKB conference, http://www.sikb.nl/11715 http://www.sikb.nl/365	Lecture about the protocol for uniform data exchange for Dutch archaeologists (SIKB 0102/Pakbon)	KNAW-DANS
26-28	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	AARG Conference 2013 http://www.decars.nl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=124&Itemid=76&lang=en	Paper "Integrating ALS, aerial prospection and ground-based survey into the study of visible and	ARUP CAS

			hidden components of post-medieval military open landscapes” “From find to structure”	
26	Valetta, Malta	TPDL 2013 www.tpd2013.info/ ARIADNE papers presented at the CRMEX workshop at TPDL2013 Malta	Paper: Quality management of 3D cultural heritage replicas with CIDOC-CRM Paper: European standards for the documentation of historic buildings and their relationship with CIDOC-CRM Paper: Mapping ICCD Archaeological Data to CIDOC-CRM: the RA Schema	PIN FORTH
October 2013				
4-5	Gothenburg, Sweden	DASISH Gothenburg workshop, 4-5 October 2013: http://dasish.eu/events/2013/wsssh	ARIADNE presentation	PIN
21	Kilkenny, Ireland	Heritage Council Workshop - Addressing digital heritage data in Ireland	ARIADNE - Coordination with national initiatives	Discovery
22	Heraklion, Greece	CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting	Presented CRMarchaeo (part of the ARIADNE Global Model) to the CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting c. 20 participants	FORTH PIN
28 - 2 Nov	Marseilles, France	Digital Heritage 2013, Int. Conf.	Paper: "A computer-assisted constraint-based system for assembling fragmented objects" (by Gregorio Palmas, Nico Pietroni, Paolo Cignoni, Roberto Scopigno, CNR)	CNR DAI

			Interviews (WP 2.1) with Conference attendees, networking. Dissemination of Fliers (DAI	
29	Rome	Presentation of ARIADNE to possible associated partners	Meeting PIN-ICCU-ICCD	PIN
November 2013				
13	Vienna	CHNT2013 conference session, "Infrastructures and services for sharing of archaeological documentation" http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/CHNT-Workshop-2013	Session organised and chaired by SRFG with support from OEAW and presentations by several partners. c. 40 researchers	SRFG OEAW KNAW-DANS CSIC FORTH Athena RC CNR Discovery SND
19-22	Thessaloniki, Greece	MTSR 2013 http://mtsr2013.teithe.gr/	Special Track on Metadata & Semantics for Cultural Collections & Applications	Athena RC UoG
19	Prato	Meeting with representatives from Getty Institute, Farallon and World Monument Fund.	Presentation of ARIADNE.	PIN
20	Graz, Austria	DARIAH Workshop DH2014 http://informationsmodellierung.uni-graz.at/de/aktuelles/dariah-workshop-dh-2014/	Short presentation of ARIADNE	OEAW
21-22	Berlin, Germany	"Facing the future" workshop, Berlin 21-22 November 2013: http://facingthefuture.gwi-berlin.de/	Presentation: "The ARIADNE approach to digital cultural heritage" c. 80-90 digital humanities researchers	PIN
20-22	Nečtiny, Czech Republic	Conference "Archaeology and the Public 7" http://www.emuzeum.cz/konference-v-cr-a-sr/archeologie-pro-budoucnost-archeologie-a-verejnost-7-2013.html	Accepted paper "Map of aerial archaeological sites"	ARUP CAS
29	Sofia, Bulgaria	Second PhD student conference "Research of cultural-historical	A presentation about AIS AKB and its development	NIAM-BAS

		heritage: provocations and prospects” http://naim.bg/en/content/news/600/857/394/	in the recent years; ARIADNE project mentioned (by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov)	
29	Rome	Seminar on Linked Open Data	Presentation of ARIADNE work on Metadata	PIN
December 2013				
2 - 4	Lund, Sweden	CAA Konferensen, CAA-Sweden https://sites.google.com/site/caasweden/konferens-2013	Invited keynote speech about ARIADNE c. 60 Participants	CNR
4	London	Meeting at British Museum	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN CYI-STARC
11	Berlin, Germany	Pelagios Gazetteer Meeting http://pelagios-project.blogspot.de/2014/01/the-day-of-pelagios-berlin-111213.html	Presentation of ARIADNE focusing on extending CIDOC-CRM	DAI, FORTH
13	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Seminar organised by Faculty of Archaeology of the University of Ljubljana about trends, developments and knowledge in archaeological archiving.	Lectures: “EASY and the archaeological data management workflow at DANS” and “Preserving the archaeological record of the Netherlands: The establishment of the e-Depot for Dutch Archaeology on standards and regulations”	KNAW-DANS`
19-21	Jodhpur, India	NCVPRIPG 2013 - National Conference on Computer Vision, Pattern Recognition, Image Processing and Graphics http://www.iitj.ac.in/ncvprpigg/	Invited keynote speech: “High-fidelity 3D models for Cultural Heritage”	CNR
January 2014				
2-4	Chicago, Illinois, USA	Annual Meetings, Archaeological Institute of America	Presentation of ARIADNE in context of Fasti Online award. Meetings with Open Context, tDAR, North Carolina Ancient	AIAC

			World Mapping Center dARMC	
20-22	Casablanca, Morocco	Africa-EU Workshop on the Fight Against Illegal Trafficking of Cultural Goods.	ARIADNE presentation	DAI
21	Catania, Italy	DCH-RP plenary meeting http://www.dch-rp.eu/	Presentation of ARIADNE; opportunities for collaboration between the two projects c. 40 participants	PIN
20-22	Berlin	DAI IT Days	ARIADNE presentation	DAI
February 2014				
6	Pisa, Italy	Italian National info day on R1 H2020-APRE	Presentation of ARIADNE in the framework of SSH Ris, Collaboration with research infrastructure projects c.250 participants	PIN
12	Timioara, Romania	Public lectures on the on-going urban archaeology in the center of Timisoara	introducing citizens the results of the on-going excavations in the center of the city within a European perspective	Arheovest
13	Frankfurt, Germany	Event of Bundesamt für Kartografie/ Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy	ARIADNE introduction, distribution of flyers	DAI
14-15	Tübingen, Germany	CAA-Germany annual meeting http://ag-caa.de	Multiple topics of interest, networking	DAI
28	Vienna	CHNT 2013 http://www.chnt.at/e-depot/	Paper "The e-Depot for Dutch Archaeology – Archiving and publication of archaeological data"	KNAW-DANS
March 2014				
17-	Seville,	Workshop at Instituto Andaluz del	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN

18	Spain	Patrimonio Historico	to Director and senior managers of the institute Cooperation agreement 10 participants	
20-21	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	15 th EAC Heritage Management Symposium, European Archaeological Council http://www.european-archaeological-council.org/16-0-Symposia.html	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 150 Archaeologists and CH managers	PIN
24-25	Sofia, Bulgaria	International conference 5th Danube Limes Brand, Project Meeting http://danubelimesbrand.org/news-events/project-meeting/	ARIADNE presentation (Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov and Nadezhda Kecheva)	NIAM-BAS
26	Prato, Italy	Meeting with delegation of Chinese Universities	Presentation of ARIADNE 25 professors from Chinese and Italian Universities and local government officers	PIN
April 2014				
2	Athens, Greece	ICRI Conference, 2 nd International Conference on Research Infrastructures. http://www.icri2014.eu/	Networking and informal presentation of ARIADNE c. 400 participants	PIN
2-4	The Hague, The Netherlands	CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting	CRMsciv1.2 was discussed (issue 229)	FORTH
7-9	Timisoara, Romania	The “other” school	Archaeological activities with school children	Arheovest
7	Athens, Greece	Launch of DARIAH-GR http://www.dias-net.gr/kickoff/?page_id=319	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 100 Greek researchers	PIN
9	Glasgow, UK	IfA 2014 http://www.archaeologists.net/co	Paper: Navigating Collaborative European Projects in Archaeology	UoY-ADS

		ference/2014info	c. 50 archaeologists	
9	Laval, France	Laval Virtual 2014 (Exhibition and conference), http://www.laval-virtual.org/en/	Invited talk on “Virtual clones for Cultural Heritage applications” at the Digital heritage Symposium	CNR-ISTI
9	Boston, Mass, USA	Meeting with DARMC (Digital Atlas of Roman and Medieval Civilisations) http://darmc.harvard.edu/icb/icb.do	Presentation of ARIADNE	AIAC
10-11	Timisoara, Romania	Bridging the Danube international conference organized by the American Research Center in Sofia	Representatives: Largest Romanian academic and research institutions, Poland, Serbia	Arheovest
12	Timisoara, Romania	Exhibition - The Dacians in the Banat plains	Exhibition on the archaeological activities of Arheovest	Arheovest
14	Leiden, The Netherlands	Odyssee symposium at the Dutch National Museum of Antiquities (RMO) : Presenting new results of research on old excavation data which was not analysed before.	Introduced ARIADNE to Dutch Archaeological project leaders during the interactive panel discussion	KNAW-DANS
16	Amersfoort, the Netherlands	RCC Symposium, the Netherlands Cultural Heritage Agency	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 60 Officers from RCE and researchers from Dutch Universities	PIN
18	Utrecht, the Netherlands	CLARIN ESFRI	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 5 CLARIN Directors	PIN
22	Paris, France	CAA 2014, “Online resources for Archaeology Research” http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/	ARIADNE Workshop	UoY-ADS, AIAC, DAI, KNAW-DANS, PIN
22-25	Paris, France	CAA 2014, partners organised a number of workshops and	Workshop “Hands-On Archaeological Conceptual	CSIC, Discovery

		<p>sessions held during the conference.</p> <p>http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/</p>	<p>Modelling 2" (CSIC)</p> <p>Session "Modelling the Archaeological Process", highly related to ARIADNE (CSIC)</p> <p>Session "GIS, a new trowel for archaeologists? The challenges of using GIS in preventive archaeology" (Discovery INRAP)</p> <p>Round table: "Virtual archaeology, the first 25 years" (PIN, CYI-STARC)</p>	<p>INRAP, PIN, CYI-STARC</p>
22-25	Paris, France	<p>CAA 2014, several partners presented individual papers or posters during the conference.</p> <p>http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/</p>	<p>Paper "The Development of Data Sharing and Open Data in Archaeology" (ADS)</p> <p>Paper "Integration of Archaeological Datasets Through the Gradual Refinement of Models" (CSIC)</p> <p>Paper: "Dykes of standards supporting polders of data / The practices used in the Netherlands for making archaeological data available and accessible" (KNAW-DANS)</p> <p>Poster - Perception and Adoption of Landscape: Recent Model and Its Use in Study of Prehistoric Settlement Strategies (ARUP CAS)</p>	<p>UoY-ADS CSIC KNAW-DANS ARUP CAS</p>
23	Timisoara, Romania	<p>Association of archaeology and ancient history</p>	<p>Weekly seminars on archaeology for students and young scholars</p>	<p>Arheovest</p>
24	Austin,	<p>SAA 2014</p>	<p>Paper: A</p>	<p>UoY-ADS</p>

	Texas, USA	http://www.saa.org/AbouttheSociety/AnnualMeeting/2014Program/tabid/1508/Default.aspx	European perspective on representing and interpreting spatial data from archaeological fieldwork as Linked Open Data	UoG FORTH
28	Rome, Italy	Presentation of IPERION CH CHARISMA partnership and other European institutions	Presentation of ARIADNE, discussion about collaboration opportunities c. 60 Researchers in conservation and preservation	PIN
May 2014				
6	Aarhus, Denmark	Meeting with Danish Humanities Research Infrastructures	Presentation of ARIADNE and discussion of collaboration opportunities c. 30 Researchers	PIN
8-10	Budapest, Hungary	"New Approaches to the Temple of Zeus at Olimpia: Architecture, sculpture, history and new technologies" http://www.archaeological.org/events/14369	Workshop on archaeological research and use of 3D graphics for study and dissemination	CNR-ISTI
25-7	Smolenice, Slovakia	18th Central European Seminar on Computer Graphics organized by TUWien	Invited talk on the ARIADNE project	CNR
26-30	Prato, Italy	"Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM", ARIADNE TNA summer school	ARIADNE TNA summer school 5 researchers	PIN, FORTH
30-31	Sandanski, Bulgaria	LIII National Archaeological Conference, May 28-31, 2013	ARIADNE development will be presented as a part of the progress of AIS AKB in 2014 (by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov)	NIAM-BAS
June 2014				
2-4	Luxembourg, Luxembourg	13 th meeting of the Member states expert group on digitisation	Networking	MIBACT-ICCU

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4	Rome, Italy	Meeting with EAGLE project http://www.eagle-network.eu/	Presentation of ARIADNE, collaboration opportunity 10 EAGLE steering committee members	PIN CYI-STARC
10	Rome, Italy	Meeting with CENIEH http://www.cenieh.es/en	Presentation of ARIADNE, collaboration opportunity 5 representatives	PIN
10-12	Grenoble, France	Colloque Patrimoine et Humanités numériques http://www.msh-alpes.fr/fr/colloque-patrimoine-humanites-numeriques	Networking	MIBACT-ICCU
11-12	Romania	Deva regional county museum, scientific event	ARIADNE presentation	Arheovest
11-13	Glasgow, UK	European Network for Archaeology and Integrated Landscape Research: workshop http://www.gla.ac.uk/schools/humanities/research/archaeologyresearch/groups/heritagephilosophypractice/	Introduction of ARIADNE, distribution of flyers	DAI
20	Rome, Italy	Tecnologie digitali per i beni culturali http://www.ambafrance-it.org/Conferenza-Tecnologie-digitali-per	Presentation of ARIADNE	CNR
23-24	Athens, Greece	Europeana Strategy meeting on Research & Tourism http://www.gr2014.eu/events/parallel-events/europeana-v3-event-%E2%80%9Ceuropaana-research-and-tourism%E2%80%9D	Networking	MIBACT-ICCU
30	Bari, Italy	Rights management in the implementation of the Digital Library	Presentation: ICCU experiences in International projects http://www.regione.puglia.it/index.php?page=calen	MIBACT-ICCU

			dario&opz=display&id=2036	
30 – 3 July	Apsley, England	ARCHES Community workshop	Presentation of ARIADNE 30 culture professionals and software developers	PIN
July 2014				
8	Lausanne, Switzerland	Digital Humanities, DH2014, GeoHumanities SIG meeting. dh2014.org	Presentation: Effective design and use of a Spatiotemporal Gazetteer	DAI
10	London, UK	EVA London 2014, “Learning Opportunities for Sharing Data in the ARIADNE Project” http://www.eva-london.org/past-eva-londons/past-eva-londons/2014	ARIADNE training workshop Presentation of ARIADNE TNA summer schools	PIN
11	Brighton, UK	A Future for our Past - Research in Digital Technologies for Arts, Heritage and Archaeology	Invited talk and presentation on ARIADNE	CNR